

MAELSTROM

MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D6.7

Report on the life cycle assessment (LCA) of the MAELSTROM automatic systems and marine litter processing technologies

October 2024

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Executive summary

The MAELSTROM project aims at testing and evaluating innovative technologies for removing marine litter (ML) in various coastal environments. It seeks to assess the impact of these technologies on ecosystems in selected demonstration sites and to evaluate the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies.

This deliverable aims at presenting the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the technologies developed for ML removal and its recycling process, conducted based on the international ISO standards 14040 and 14044 (ISO14040, 2006; ISO14044, 2006).

In this sense, two ML cleaning technologies, a Bubble Barrier column, and a seabed cleaning platform, one segregation technology, the AI-driven Robotic system, as well as three recycling technologies, thermoplastics treatment through additives and crushing, treatment of plastics and organic waste that is difficult to recycle through crushing and pressing and temperature pyrolysis treatment have been evaluated.

This deliverable is organized into the following sections: in the first section, it introduces the issue at hand and outlines the objectives of the deliverable. The second section offers a comprehensive description of all MAELSTROM project technologies that have been subject to environmental analysis. The third section details the methodological approach employed in these analyses. The fourth section presents a life cycle analysis, including all inventories provided by project partners, which encompass the inputs and outputs of the technologies throughout their life cycle. The fifth section focuses on the life cycle assessment, delineating the impact categories selected to evaluate the environmental performance of the MAELSTROM technologies. The sixth section provides the results of the analyses conducted using the tool SimaPro for LCA. Subsequently, the seventh section engages in an in-depth discussion of the inherent benefits of removing plastics from coastal ecosystems. Finally, the eighth section summarizes the conclusive findings of the study.

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Abbreviations

AC	Acidification
Ade	Resource use, minerals, and metals
ADff	Resource use, fossils
AI	Artificial intelligence
APOS	Allocation at the point of substitution
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CED-nr	Cumulative Energy Demand - non renewable
CED-r	Cumulative Energy Demand - renewable
EC	European Commission
EF	Eutrophication, freshwater
EM	Eutrophication, marine
ET	Eutrophication, terrestrial
ETX	Ecotoxicity, freshwater
FU	Functional unit
GLO	Global
GW	Climate change
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene
HTc	Human toxicity, cancer
HTnc	Human toxicity, non-cancer
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
LU	Land use
ML	Marine litter
Mt	Million tons
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
P	Piece (in the inventories, kg/ ρ refers to kg per piece)
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PM	Particulate matter
PP	Polypropylene
PV	Photovoltaic system
RER	Europa
RoW	Rest of World
Tkm	Ton-kilometer
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
WU	Water use

1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

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3 Aim of the Deliverable

The global consumption of plastics is expected to increase from 460 million tons (Mt) in 2019 to 1,231 Mt in 2060 if bold policies in this regard are not implemented. Most of this escalation is expected to occur in developing and emerging countries. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)¹ countries will produce much more plastic waste per person (238 kg per year on average in 2060) than non-OECD countries (77 kg). At the same time, plastic leakage into the environment is expected to double and plastic waste in natural ecosystems such as oceans and rivers will triple (from 353 Mt in 2019 to 1,014 Mt in 2060), posing severe pollution challenges (OECD, 2022). Additionally, according to estimates, there could be more plastic than fish in the oceans by 2050 if significant action is not taken to address the problem of Marine Litter (ML) (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2022).

Throughout history, humanity has maintained an ambivalent relationship with the oceans and seas, exploiting their natural resources and contributing to pollution and degradation. In the past, a lack of environmental awareness and effective regulations led to a significant accumulation of litter in marine environments.

Currently, the adverse effects on marine biodiversity are causing significant concern among institutions and the general community. ML can destroy aquatic habitats, harm marine life, and contaminate the food chain. For example, animals and birds can ingest plastics, which can cause damage to their health and, in extreme cases, the death. Plastic pollution negatively affects marine ecosystems, altering the balance of biodiversity of aquatic communities (Thushari & Senevirathna, 2020; Tursi et al., 2022). Ultimately, plastic contamination of the food chain also affects humans through ingestion of fish (Mamun et al., 2023).

Growing awareness about the importance of the oceans and the need to preserve them has contributed to taking actions to manage marine waste. Innovative technologies have been developed for the collection and recycling of ocean waste. Up to 80% of ML is estimated to be made of plastics, so there is significant potential to recycle a substantial portion of these materials.

¹ 38 member countries spread across the globe, encompassing North America, South America, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific region, collectively form the OECD.

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With an eye toward the future, the environmental assessment of ML collection and recycling technologies will be crucial to ensuring our oceans' health and marine ecosystems' sustainability.

New technological innovations, such as autonomous vehicles and advanced tracking systems, are being developed to address the problem of ML more effectively. An example of this, is the MAELSTROM project, which strives to provide diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy, by integrating various technologies into European coastal ecosystems emphasizing circular economy principles and social benefits.

MAELSTROM project' key objectives include assessing the distribution and impact of ML on valuable ecosystems, designing scalable and sustainable technologies to identify, remove and classify ML, as well as raising public awareness and collaborating with similar projects within and outside the European Union.

This deliverable presents a detailed evaluation of the environmental impacts of the MAELSTROM technologies that have been developed within the framework of the MAELSTROM project for the collection and recycling of ML applying a life cycle approach. The idea behind is to identify the environmental impacts of each technology towards the identification of the most relevant areas of improvement for each technology, thus enabling the reduction of the overall environmental footprint of the MAELSTROM project technologies.

4 MAESLTROM technologies description

4.1 Cleaning technologies

4.1.1 Bubble Barrier

The Bubble Barrier offers a solution to the problem of plastic waste floating on the surface and in the water column of rivers and canals. This technology combines a bubble curtain with a waste collection system consisting of hoses, a compressor and air filters enclosed in one container, and a collection system.

The technology can work in continuous mode and involves using a flexible rubber air tube with perforations combined with an integrated reinforcement. The design of the hose(s) depends on the installation site. The hose(s) sinks automatically and does not need additional anchorage, but it's recommended for safety.

To create the bubble curtain, the flexible hose(s) is connected to a compressed air system installed in containers on land and includes suitable filters to maintain high air quality standards. The generated bubbles carry the suspended plastic waste to the surface and generate flow in the surficial layer of the water that prevents the debris from flowing downstream. The plastic waste is retained on the riverside and collected in the collection system.

Filtered plastic and other waste will be collected in the collection system into big bags or a trolley. This system is typically moored with rails to a quay, but alternative mooring systems, adapted to the location, permits, and type of land/dock, are considered. It is important to mention that the use of the mooring platform, as used within the Maelstrom project, is not necessary in most cases, for this reason, it has not been included in the LCA. The trolley is equipped with wheels for easy transport to the shore. If necessary, an electric winch on land could be used to support transportation if the trolley becomes too heavy, or the emptying frequency is high.

This technology can remove plastic waste ranging from 1 mm to 1 m. It requires very little maintenance, and almost no maintenance is necessary during the first five years, making it highly advantageous. However, because the system must adapt to where it is installed, a design must be made for each location. The deployment can also vary depending on the width and depth of the river.

For the operation of the air compressor, grid energy is used. The Great Bubble Barrier always strongly suggest the use of renewable energy to its clients. In this sense, the MAELSTROM project proposes co-energizing the Bubble Barrier system through

photovoltaic system (PV). For this, a small floating PV system and a roof installed PV system have been installed near the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde. The design of the floating PV system consists of a standard PV system on a floating dock, installed near the catchment system. The design of the roof-installed PV system consists of several components: PV panels, inverter, and structure.

The solar panels generate electricity by absorbing solar radiation in monocrystalline silicon crystals, thus creating electricity as a flow of charges. Each module is connected in series to form a string attached to other strings in parallel, creating the PV system. The on-land solar panels are placed on a rooftop facing the South orientation and inclined to be perpendicular to the sun for as long as possible to maximize electricity generation. The panels are also connected to the electricity grid to export any extra electricity generated. The floating solar panels work similarly, with the difference that they are installed on a floating dock closer to the Bubble Barrier and co-power the compressor directly without being connected to the electricity grid.

4.1.2 Seabed cleaning platform

The seabed cleaning platform is a novel approach to cleaning seabed and lower water columns using cable robotics. This innovative solution allows for the targeted removal of identified litter with the help of a robotized device, making the process more efficient. The system consists of a cable-based underwater robot that is installed and operated from a floating barge. It is equipped with specialized cleaning tools that can selectively remove legacy small (micro-plastics <5 mm) and oversized items from the ocean floor and floating plastics in the lower water column, benefiting the marine ecosystem.

The seabed cleaning platform has specific requirements and components. In this sense, the layout of the cable-based robotic platform consists of a floating barge, supporting structures, a mobile platform (robot), a standard crane with a basket, a control room, a working room, and a power generator.

The floating platform is made up of rigidly connected pontoons. The floating barge is designed for still waters and sea operations, and its maximum operating depth depends on the floating barge's width. To ensure stability, the floating barge is anchored to the seafloor with feet or wire anchors, depending on the depth of cleaning. The floating barge is moved from spot to spot by a tugboat, with manoeuvrability depending on the tug master and the characteristics of the tug, approved by the harbour master for the selected navigation zones.

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Four sets of supporting structures integrate the winches, the pulleys that guide the cables from the winches to the mobile platform, and the force sensors to monitor cable tensions. The mobile platform has grippers, perception cameras, and sensors for identifying and removing ML. The mobile platform has a gripper for large objects and an aspiration system for small objects. An umbilical cable guides power and communication cables to the mobile platform.

Also, the technology includes a control room that integrates the electrical cabinet and the working room for operators and a power generator. The control room contains an electrical cabinet with the power supply (drive, amplifier, converter, etc.) and control (computer, field bus interface, etc.) necessary for the winch and trolley motors verticals.

By working the robot together with a crane located on the barge, which helps manipulate a basket from the bottom of the water to the surface. This makes handling marine remains easier and the robot can better place the debris in the basket. Once the basket is full, the crane can lift it back onto the barge.

The solution's innovation focuses on the optimal placement of winches and pulleys on the floating barge and the design of the underwater robot frame to fulfil various requirements. These include maximizing the cable robot's workspace at different depths, easy operability, compact size to avoid collisions, and the ability to balance off-centred water current forces.

4.2 Segregation and recycling technologies

4.2.1 AI-driven Robotic system

The development of a waste separation robot solution based on artificial intelligence (AI) is aimed at addressing the pressing need for efficient and accurate waste separation. The solution incorporates advanced AI algorithms to enable the robot to recognize, identify, and separate various types of waste, including plastics, packaging, ML, construction waste, textiles, and more. With the ability to distinguish between different kinds of waste, the solution is expected to significantly reduce the amount of waste that ends up in landfills and improve the recycling process. The waste separation robot solution represents a significant step towards a more sustainable and eco-friendly future.

The sorting robot cell consists of three main components. The first component is the AI sensing and classification unit, which includes a Redeye NIR unit, 3D camera, AI

computer, galvanized steel frame, and light shields. The second component is the robotic unit, which consists of an Omron robot, an electrical cabinet with PLC, electrical cables, a pneumatic "spring" suction cup, a galvanized steel frame, galvanized steel mesh doors, and two acrylic protectors. Finally, the third component is the conveyor belts, consisting of two belts, 1 kW motors, reducers, stainless steel frames with aluminium feet, an electrical cabinet, a touch screen, and cables. The robot detects and separates objects and places them in cubes explicitly designed for the process. The number of cubes placed on the sides of the robot depends on the size of the robot frame, aiming to reduce the distance between the belt and the cube and maximize the efficiency of the technology. It is important to note that the robot's efficiency is affected by how the waste is placed on the belt and the speed of the belt. These parameters are optimized to achieve a high separation performance. The separated material undergoes three recycling processes (blue boxes) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Flow diagram for the segregation and recycling technologies

In this case, it is important to mention that all the components have been purchased from external companies. Even so, in this case, like the two cleaning technologies, the LCA has also considered manufacturing the equipment. However, the AI training has been excluded from the analysis.

4.2.2 Thermoplastic recycling (additivation and shredding)

This technology aims at processing diverse and heterogeneous marine plastic waste (such as PET, LDPE, HDPE, PS, and PP) that has been collected and separated and is likely to be extensively degraded by the effects of saltwater and sunlight. Such waste is anticipated to exhibit a wide range of properties, depending on the location of its collection and the extent of degradation. Reclaimed thermoplastic materials must be enhanced by adding chemicals and fibres (either recycled or natural) to create high-performance composite materials.

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The recycling begins after the plastic recovered from ML has been sorted and cleaned. The first step is to shred the recovered plastic in a mill. All the materials introduced are recovered during this process, thus avoiding waste.

The second stage is compounding. During this stage, the crushed material is introduced into the hopper of the twin screw extruder. The extrusion consists of introducing the plastic into a barrel with two corotating twin screws, where the plastic melts and advances through the screws. In this process, the plastic is mixed with additives or fibreglass (which is the case for this study) to recover its properties. The mixture exits the extrusion die as a continuous filament and cools into a water bath. Finally, this filament is dragged to a pellet mill and cut to 3mm. Although, when the extruder machine is turned on, a loss of material occurs, this material can be recovered as post-processed recycled plastic, carrying out a crushing process and reincorporation into the original material mixture in the hopper.

The last stage included in this recycling technology is injection. At this stage, the reformulated pellet is introduced into the hopper of the injection machine to manufacture an injected part. The injection process involves introducing the plastic into a barrel with a screw. The plastic melts and advances to the injection cavity, where once filled, it is pushed by the screw toward the nozzle at very high pressure. The nozzle is attached to a mold at a temperature below that of the barrel and below the melting temperature of the plastic. Molten plastic enters the mold under high pressure and fills the cavity to the part's geometry. The piece cools in seconds, and the press that holds the mold is opened. The piece is unmoulded, and the final product is obtained. As in the previous stage, small amounts of waste can be obtained that can be reintroduced into the process after grinding.

4.2.3 Hard to recycle plastics (thermal press molding)

This method is innovative for recycling fibre-reinforced composites and thermosetting matrix rigid foams, which would otherwise go to landfills. With a non-polluting mechanical process, the waste is transformed into Recomplax panels, using a lower percentage of virgin raw materials. Recomplax panels can be worked like wood: calibrated, sanded, laminated, milled, glued, and varnished.

This process starts once the AI sorting robot removes the detected thermoplastics from the recycling belt. What is left continues its journey in the recycling line, where trained manual operators collect valuable waste. This manually separated waste is mixed with the larger ones collected manually at the entry point of the recycling lane.

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The process itself of recycling hard-to-recycle materials is done in different steps. First, part of the separated waste is crushed, while the ferrous and non-ferrous metals are separated and recovered. The waste is then further reduced into chips by a rotary paddle mill, sorted and sent to storage. In the second stage, a mixture is produced with the same or different raw materials, feeding them into a turbo mixer where a small percentage of binding agent/compatibilizer is added, along with natural oxide colorants or other additives (e.g., antibacterial properties, graphite for antistatic, etc.). This mixture is loaded into a panel mold, subjected to temperature and high pressure, and synthesized on a panel. Finally, the panel undergoes a calibration or surface coating process like products of virgin origin.

4.2.4 Temperature pyrolysis

The pyrolysis system used as a basis for the LCA data input (inventory tables) in the MAELSTROM project is an industrial scale plant designed specifically to process plastic waste streams collected through sorting of municipal waste.

The full-scale plant has two main functions: a pyrolysis reactor used to establish the high-temperature and oxygen-free environment necessary for pyrolysis reactions to take place, and a condenser system to collect volatilized hydrocarbons as pyrolysis liquid. But apart from those main functions, all necessary auxiliary functions including material transport, syngas processing, solid residue handling, mechanical sorting etc. are also included in the LCA data input.

Thorough calculations performed for this plant form the basis for the LCA-input in the MAELSTROM project, but to estimate processing of ML an experiment was conducted to establish a correlation between sorted municipal waste and ML input material.

In the experiment ML material sorted in the MAELSTROM project was processed in the Makeen test-reactor system, which operates on the same principles as the full-scale plant. Through the experiment the material was found to be suitable for processing, and the content of Marine Diesel in the products was determined by distillation of the pyrolysis liquid. It should be noted that because no fully sorted ML material was available yet in the Maelstrom project, the received material was sorted at Makeen by removing unsuitable feedstock with a focus on providing enough material for a full test.

The end product of this process is marine diesel fuel that meets ISO 8217 DMA and DMB class.

5 Methodological approach

The LCA methodology determines the environmental impacts of a product, process, or service through its entire life cycle. This means that the environmental impacts are calculated by considering the relevant inputs and outputs of the product, process, or service in terms of mass and energy balance. To ensure transparency when applying the LCA methodology, mainly two standards are provided by the ISO:

- ISO 14040:2006 - Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Principles and framework (ISO 14040, 2006).
- ISO 14044:2006 - Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Requirements and guidelines (ISO 14044, 2006).

The following four phases must be contemplated for conducting a LCA (Figure 2):

1. **The goal & scope definition:** In this first phase, the reasons for carrying out the study (goal) and the product system to be studied (scope) are defined. In addition, the following issues must be described: the intended audience, the functional unit (FU), the system boundaries, the data quality requirements, as well as the assumptions and limitations to be considered in the study.
2. **The inventory analysis:** This phase refers to the data collection related to the product, process, or service. This means that information related to raw materials and energy inputs, products or co-products, emissions and waste must be gathered.
3. **The impact assessment:** This phase refers to the calculation of the potential environmental impacts related to the product, process or service considering the previously generated inventory. If required, previously defined goal & scope can be reviewed during this phase.
4. **The interpretation of the results:** In this phase, an interpretation of the results is accomplished. Results must be consistent with the goal and scope. Considering these results, a set of conclusions and recommendations to guide future actions are outlined.

Figure 2. Life cycle assessment methodology phases and application (ISO14040, 2006)

5.1 Goal & scope definition

5.1.1 Goal of the study

5.1.1.1 Intended applications

The definition of the study's goal identifies the reasons for carrying out the assessment. The overarching aim of the MAELSTROM project is to address the complex challenge of sustainable treatment and disposal of ML by offering diversified solutions. To this end, the environmental study is expected to be aligned with the project's general objective. Specifically, the MAELSTROM project investigates different technologies to eliminate ML. In this sense, the possibility of using two ML elimination technologies has been evaluated: a Bubble Barrier column and a seabed cleaning platform. On the other hand, ML segregation involves the use of an AI-driven robot to differentiate plastics from other retrieved materials. Finally, some of the collected waste undergo various recycling processes, including thermoplastic recycling treatment (additivation and shredding), hard-to-recycle plastics and organic waste treatment (shredding and press moulding), and temperature pyrolysis treatment.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the environmental impacts of the MAELSTROM technologies developed and applied for the elimination and recycling of ML, applying the life cycle approach.

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5.1.1.2 Target audience

The LCA can help companies understand the environmental impacts, and the results obtained can contribute to making better decisions regarding sustainability and tracking improvements over time. Therefore, it is important to determine the main stakeholders interested in the sustainability results.

The main target audience of the environmental assessment study is the MAELSTROM project consortium and the EC. The LCA results can also be shared with other interested parties, including researchers, companies focused on cleaning coasts and rivers, and companies focused on waste segregation and recycling plastics and organic waste.

The primary target audience are project partners, the European Commission, and the stakeholders interested in understanding the environmental impacts of different ML cleaning, segregation and recycling technologies.

5.1.2 Scope of the study

The scope must describe the study in detail. The study's scope must provide information on the function of the product/service/technology, the Functional Unit (FU) and the reference flow, a description of the system and system boundaries, the allocation and calculation methods, the limitations and assumptions, and data quality requirements, among others.

5.1.2.1 Functional unit

The application of the product/service/technology must be identified to define the FU of the analysis. The FU is a critical element that must be carefully chosen to quantify the specific function, to be aligned with the objective, to be precise and sufficiently comparable, and to be selected through the verification and validation of the available inventory data while considering any possible restrictions. The FU must provide a reference for all the inputs and outputs of the studied system and must be defined considering the following aspects:

WHAT?	The function or service
HOW MUCH?	The number of functions or service
HOW?	The quality of the service
UNTIL WHEN?	The useful life of the service

Although using the quantity of the final products as the FU is often recommended, the MAELSTROM project aims to eliminate and treat ML. Therefore, the amount of ML

removed has been chosen as the FU to reach all the technologies involved in the project. Moreover, all the amount of waste eliminated through the cleaning technologies of the aquatic ecosystems is considered ML. However, once these waste materials are separated using segregation technologies, only the waste specifically relevant to each recycling process is considered. Other residues not aligned with the project's objectives have been treated as avoided products or waste. An appropriate treatment process has been selected to treat these by-products/wastes in this case. This decision guarantees that the assessment considers the project's total impact on the marine environment, providing a reference for all inputs and outputs of the technologies. Such an approach provides valuable insights into the environmental impact of the MAELSTROM project, allowing stakeholders to make informed decisions on marine waste treatment and management.

In the MAELSTROM project, it has been determined that the FU is 1kg of dry ML removed for the cleaning technologies and 1kg of residue treated for the recycling technologies.

5.1.2.2 System boundaries

The system boundaries define which processes are included or excluded from the analysis. The system boundaries can be presented by means of a flow chart where the considered processes and the relationships between them are included, considering the cut-off criteria. The cut-off criteria establish which parts of the system are excluded from the analysed system. In some cases, it is necessary to use a combination of different cut-off criteria to correctly define the system boundaries (i.e., mass, impact).

Different system boundaries can be used in LCA analyses (Figure 3):

- Cradle-to-Grave: From the raw material extraction and up to the end of the product's useful life.
- Cradle-to-Gate: From the raw material extraction to the production phase (factory gate).
- Gate-to-Grave: It includes the steps of use and end of life.
- Gate-to-Gate: It includes only the production phase.
- Cradle-to-cradle: Includes recovery and recirculation of raw materials within the process.

Figure 3 Different LCA approaches

In Figure 4, the system boundaries for the MAELSTROM technologies are presented:

Figure 4 System boundaries for the MAELSTROM project

While a complete LCA is ideal in most cases, this report is focused on analysing ML cleaning and treatment technologies which are critical to meet MAELSTROM project goals. In addition, since the scale of the cleaning and recycling technologies is not the same (scaled-up and laboratory level, respectively), the technologies have been analysed separately, and therefore, two system boundaries have been considered depending on the technology under study.

On the one hand, a **cradle-to-gate approach has been selected for the cleaning and segregation technologies** (Figure 5). This approach considers the extraction of the raw materials necessary to produce the equipment (background processes), the manufacture and installation of the equipment, the operation for the collection and segregation of the ML and the dismantling. Since the environmental analysis has been done for each technology separately, a cradle-to-grave approach cannot be

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applied since the use and disposal of the products (ML) have not been considered at that same stage but in other subsequent processes (ML recycling processes).

On the other hand, a **gate-to-gate approach** has been considered for recycling technologies (Figure 6), including only the equipment's operation without considering capital goods but considering the extraction of raw materials to produce chemicals used in operation (background processes). The reason is that MAESLTROM recycling technologies will operate only at the laboratory level, and the equipment's were purchased in advance. In this sense, the equipment has not been considered in the analysis since the data for the equipment could not be reliable.

Figure 5 General system boundaries for the cleaning and segregation technologies

Figure 6 General system boundaries for the recycling technologies

A burden-free input has been assumed to analyse cleaning, segregation, and recycling technologies. First, ML has been treated as waste and it can be considered an input with no environmental charge. On the other hand, the impact of the stages prior to the segregation and recycling stages has not been considered since each technology has been evaluated separately. This approach allows a better understanding of the specific impact of each technology without the consideration of additional impacts from the previous stages.

Regarding the comparison between the MAELSTROM technologies and their traditional counterparts, even if this is usually conducted in LCA studies to show the improvements in terms of environmental impacts, in this case, this type of analysis has not been performed. On the one hand, when it comes to cleaning technologies

for ecosystems, it is often difficult to find a conventional technology that can effectively clean these areas. This is because much of the cleaning is currently being done manually, making it difficult to determine its environmental performance. On the other hand, some alternative routes for waste management can be considered for recycling technologies, including a combination of landfill and incineration processes or other currently applied methods. However, conducting a comparative analysis of these technologies is not feasible for several reasons, with the scale used in the studies being the primary concern. The recycling technologies developed within the project have been evaluated at the laboratory level. In contrast, information on alternative technologies from bibliographies and databases is typically normalized for larger scales, such as the industrial level. The level of detail across different scenarios must be similar to ensure fairness and consistency in the comparative analysis. However, obtaining the necessary data for the alternative technologies with the same level of detail as for the technologies developed in the framework of the project is a challenge. Considering this, it becomes evident that a tailored approach, focusing on the individual analysis of each technology and assessing its specific impacts throughout the life cycle, is more appropriate than attempting a broad comparative analysis. This approach enables a comprehensive understanding of the environmental implications of the technologies and aligns with the project's ultimate goal of effectively removing and treating ML while minimizing adverse effects.

System boundaries for cleaning and segregation technologies include: the extraction of raw materials, the operation and the manufacture and dismantling of equipment. By contrast, system boundaries for recycling technologies include: the extraction of the raw material for the production of energy and chemicals used in the process and the use and maintenance of the equipment.

5.1.2.3 Allocation rules

Modern systems typically generate multiple useful products; therefore, it is crucial to distribute the system's resource usage and the environmental impacts among these products. In this sense, defining an allocation method in multi-product systems is necessary. The allocation method's selection must be made considering the study's goal and the system boundaries of the analysed product. The different approaches adopted for the allocation method are presented below (ISO/TR 14049, 2012):

- **System expansion** is when all the functions corresponding to the multiple products involved in the multifunctionality issue are maintained; in this case, the FU is not isolated but expanded.
- **Substitution method** in which multifunctionality is resolved by reducing multi-product systems to single-product systems by subtracting the avoided charges related to the co-products that are not part of the FU.
- **Partitioning method** in which the inputs and outputs of a process are related to the relevant products and by-products. In this case, the assignment can be done according to the following rules:
 - **Mass Allocation:** the inputs and outputs of a process are allocated to all its products in proportion to their mass.
 - **Energy assignment:** the inputs and outputs of a process are assigned to all its products according to their calorific value.
 - **Economic allocation:** the inputs and outputs of a process are allocated to all its products according to their market value.
 - **Assignment by other rules:** the inputs and outputs of a process are allocated to all its products according to different criteria like exergy, substance content, etc.

The ISO 14044 standard establishes the following preferential criteria (ISO14040, 2006):

- **Step 1:** Whenever possible, the allocation should be avoided by dividing the unit process into two or more threads, collecting the input and output data related to these threads, or extending the product system to include the functions additions related to co-products.
- **Step 2:** When an allocation cannot be avoided, the inputs and outputs of the system should be separated between its different products or functions in a way that reflects the physical relationships between them.
- **Step 3:** Where the physical relationship cannot be established or used as a basis for allocation, inputs between products and functions should be allocated to reflect other connections between them.

In the case of cleaning and segregation technologies, it is considered that a single product (ML) is obtained. The same goes for two of the recycling technologies. In this sense, composite is obtained in the case of thermoplastics recycling technology, while, in the case of hard-to-recycle technology, laminated/panel plastics products are obtained. On the other hand, three products are obtained for pyrolysis: marine fuel, naphtha, and char. Even so, since the analysis of recycling technologies does not

focus on the output but on the input, it would not be necessary to consider an allocation method. Furthermore, since all the outputs from the process can be sold for further processing (into either fuel, plastic production, fertilizer, or heat production), they are not modelled in this system.

For this analysis, no allocation rules have been considered.

5.1.2.4 Cut-off criteria

It is recommended to consider all the processes and flows included in the system under study. When conducting a LCA, it is important to consider all processes and flows in the system. However, not all of them may be quantitatively relevant, and cut-off criteria can be used to exclude certain inputs and outputs, non-relevant life cycle stages, and specific processes and products. These criteria should be transparently documented and justified in the report. Different criteria, such as mass, energy, and environmental importance, can be used, and it is recommended to consider all of them to avoid excluding important inputs from the analysis. To define which cut-off criteria will be established in an analysis, the following procedure must be followed (Sustainable Minds, 2018):

- It is recommended to include all the inputs and outputs of the process. In the case of those data are not available, certain conservative assumptions should be made with average, generic or indirect data. Any assumptions that are considered must be documented.
- Those inputs that can release high amounts of substances into the air, water or soil that can generate a significant environmental impact cannot be excluded. However, in specific cases of missing information, the cut-off criteria for inputs should be very low (1-5%).
- Hazardous and toxic substances for human health and/or the environment must be identified and considered in the analysis, although this flow is under the cut-off criterion of 1% of the total mass.

However, due to the LCA complexity, making assumptions and establishing limitations is often necessary to simplify the analysis. It is important to note that while these simplifications may be necessary, it is essential to make them as accurate as possible to ensure that the LCA results are meaningful and reliable. Also, it is required to clearly communicate these assumptions and limitations to maintain transparency

and allow for appropriate interpretation of the MAELSTROM project findings. The assumptions and limitations established within the study are listed below:

- It is considered that the technologies have been installed close to where the equipment have been manufactured, assuming a distance of 100 km.
- A distance of 300 km has been considered to transport the equipment to the disposal plants.
- Only the manufacturing of equipment for cleaning and segregation technologies have been considered. On the other hand, equipment for recycling technologies have been excluded since they have been purchased in advance rather than manufactured within the project.
- The analyses for the recycling technologies have been made considering the laboratory data.
- Comparative analyses have not been carried out.
- A burden-free input has been assumed to analyse technologies.
- The final products have been considered to be outside the system boundaries.

This study has not considered systematic cut-off criteria (whether by mass, energy, or environmental importance). However, the limitations and assumptions that have been made to carry out the analysis have been explained.

5.1.2.5 Data quality requirements

Main types and data sources must be identified during the scope definition stage. Foreground and background data quality requirements include the following parameters: coverage, precision, completeness, representativeness, consistency, reproducibility, sources, and uncertainty (ISO/TR 14049, 2012). The data quality objectives must define the representativeness needs, including temporal, geographic, technological, and physical aspects. The inventory data quality has been studied following the criteria described in Table 1.

Table 1 Data quality requirements

Ranking	Data accuracy indicator
1	Data was obtained directly from the company.
2	Data was estimated from company data.
3	Data was estimated from literature or commercial databases.
Ranking	Geographical representativeness indicator
1	Data was obtained from the geographical area of the study.
2	Data was obtained from a wider geographical area, which includes the study area.
3	Data was obtained from another or unknown geographical area.
Ranking	Temporal representativeness indicator
1	Data are less than 5 years old.
2	Data are between 5 and 10 years old.
3	Data are more than 10 years old or are an unknown date.
Ranking	Dataset representativeness indicator
1	The selected dataset is representative.
2	The selected dataset is representative for a similar material or process.
3	The selected dataset is not representative.

6 Life cycle inventory analysis

The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is a fundamental step of the LCA that provides a comprehensive and detailed inventory of inputs and outputs of a product or service throughout its life cycle. It involves identifying and quantifying all the materials, energy, and emissions associated with the various stages of a product's life, from raw material extraction, production, distribution, use, and disposal or recycling. The LCI provides a detailed account of the environmental profile of a product and serves as a foundation for the subsequent phases of LCA, such as impact assessment and interpretation.

In this phase, the collection of data (inputs and outputs) related to the product, process or service must be completed. Table 2 shows an example of the types of inputs and outputs of a process.

Table 2 Process inputs and outputs necessary to calculate the environmental impacts

INPUTS	OUTPUTS
Energy consumption: all inputs related to energy (electricity, natural gas, etc.).	Emissions to air: all substances released into the atmosphere.
Raw materials: materials present in the product composition.	Emissions to water: all substances that are released to water streams.
Auxiliary materials: materials needed to manufacture the product.	Emissions to soil: all substances filtered into the soil.
Water consumption: all inputs related to water.	Waste: material flows to treatment.
Transport: transport needed for all materials and waste.	Products: final product or intermediate product.

The raw data obtained in the collection stage must meet the quality criteria established (Table 1) before calculating the LCI. For that, the data obtained is subjected to a process that includes the following:

- Data validation by calculating the mass or energy balance and comparing it with similar data.
- Relation of data with unitary processes.
- Relation of data with the FU.

It is advisable to use data obtained directly from the process under study (through in situ measurements, material and energy balances, interviews with those involved in the production chain, recognised databases, or bibliographic sources) whenever possible. However, issues with the initially defined conditions may be identified as the inventory data collection progresses. In such instances, the data requirements or limitations may need to be redefined, or a change in system boundaries or data collection procedures may be required to meet the study objective. In more complex cases, it may even be necessary to review or redefine the definition of the goal or scope of the study. These changes and any restrictions during data collection should be documented accordingly.

To calculate the inventory data, additional tables have been introduced to compile the general information of the process (Figure 7). In addition, for the MAELSTROM project, an Excel has been prepared to gather the LCI with all the inputs and outputs, as can be seen in Figure 8 for cleaning and segregation technologies and Figure 9 for recycling technologies.

Cleaning technologies		
	Unit	Value
Equipment weight	kg or tons	
Installation location		
Annual days of operation	days/year	
Daily operation time	hours/day	
Daily amount of ML collected	kg/day	
Lifespan of equipment	years	
Segregation technologies		
Equipment weight	kg or tons	
Installation location		
Annual days of operation	days/year	
Daily operation time	hours/day	
Daily amount of ML segregated	kg/day	
Daily amount of ML to be recycled	kg/day	
Lifespan of equipment	years	

Figure 7 General data as part of the LCI template

Name stage	Type flow	Name flow	Simapro name	LCA amount	LCA unit per unit	Source (LCA)	Comments
Equipment manufacturing							
Equipment 1							
Equipment manufacturing	input - raw materials				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - water				kg or m3 per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - energy				kWh or MJ per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - transport				kg*km per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - product				unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - air emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - water emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - soil emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - waste				kg or m3 per unit		
Equipment 2							
Equipment manufacturing	input - raw materials				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - water				kg or m3 per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - energy				kWh or MJ per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	input - transport				kg*km per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - product				unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - air emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - water emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - soil emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment manufacturing	Output - waste				kg or m3 per unit		
Equipment transport							
Equipment transport	Input - distance		Distance		km		
Equipment transport	Input - vehicle		Vehicle type		Vehicle type		
Equipment transport	Input- transported quantity		Transported quantity		kg or m3		
Equipment transport	Input - fuel		Fuel		kg		
Equipment transport	Output product				kg or cm2 or unit		
Equipment installation							
Equipment installation	input - raw materials				kg or L per unit		
Equipment installation	input - water				kg or m3 per unit		
Equipment installation	input - energy				kWh or MJ per unit		
Equipment installation	Output - product				unit		
Equipment installation	Output - air emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment installation	Output - water emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment installation	Output - soil emissions				kg or L per unit		
Equipment installation	Output - waste				kg or m3 per unit		
Use & Maintenance							
Use & Maintenance	input - raw materials				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	input - water				kg or m3 per FU		
Use & Maintenance	input - energy				kWh or MJ per FU		
Use & Maintenance	input - ML transport				kg*km per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - product				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - air emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - water emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - soil emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - waste				kg or m3 per FU		
Use & Maintenance							
Transportation to EoL							
Transportation to EoL	Input - distance		Distance		km		
Transportation to EoL	Input - vehicle		Vehicle type		Vehicle type		
Transportation to EoL	Input - transported quantity		Transported quantity		kg or m3		
Transportation to EoL	Input - fuel		Fuel		kg		
Transportation to EoL	Output product				kg or cm2 or unit		
Transportation to EoL							
EoL equipment							
EoL equipment	Waste - Landfill				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment	Waste - Landfill				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment	Waste - Incineration				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment	Waste - Incineration				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment	Waste - Recycle				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment	Waste - Recycle				kg or m3 or %		
EoL equipment							

Figure 8 LCI template to collect the inventory data for cleaning and segregation technologies

Name stage	Type flow	Name flow	Simapro name	LCA amount	LCA unit per unit	Source (LCA)	Comments
ML transport							
ML transport	input - distance		Distance		km		
ML transport	input - vehicle		Vehicle type		Vehicle type		
ML transport	input - transported quantity		Transported quantity		kg or m3		
ML transport	input - fuel		Fuel		kg		
ML transport	Output product				kg or cm2 or unit		
Name stage	Type flow	Name flow	Simapro name	LCA amount	LCA unit per unit	Source (LCA)	Comments
Name stage	Type flow	Name flow	Simapro name	LCA amount	LCA unit per FU	Source (LCA)	Comments
Use & Maintenance							
Use & Maintenance	input - raw materials				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	input - water				kg or m3 per FU		
Use & Maintenance	input - energy				kWh or MJ per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - product				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - air emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - water emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - soil emissions				kg or L per FU		
Use & Maintenance	Output - waste				kg or m3 per FU		
Use & Maintenance							

Figure 9 LCI template to collect inventory data for the recycling technologies

Foreground data related to the processes developed in the framework of the MAELSTROM project have been provided by the project partners (at the laboratory, pilot plant and industrial scale). Background data have been obtained from specific LCA databases (e.g., Ecoinvent²) and the literature.

6.1 Cleaning technologies

6.1.1 Bubble Barrier

For the Bubble Barrier installation, all inventory data has been successfully collected. MAELSTROM Partners TGBB and UOM have provided the list of components used for the installation in Vila do Conde, Portugal, and their quantities. Estimations were made regarding equipment operation and ML collected. The life cycle inventory considers the first year of operation and maintenance of the Bubble Barrier.

The collected ML have been estimated to be treated as follows: approximately 35% is undergo various recycling processes for reuse, while 50% is sent to a sanitary landfill for proper disposal. The remaining 15% is treated through incineration as part of the waste management process.

The following tables show the inventory data gathered for general information (Table 3) and the equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling (Table 4).

² The ecoinvent database is a library of activities representing industrial or agricultural processes, each generating a resulting product. The ecoinvent database supports a broad and diverse range of sustainability assessments.

Table 3 General information for the Bubble Barrier

General information	Value
Installation location	Vila do Conde
Annual operation time	8500 h
Lifespan of the Bubble Barrier	15 years
Annual amount of ML collected	200.000 kg/year
Total plastic collected during the lifespan	3.000.000 kg

Table 4 Inventory data for the Bubble Barrier (equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Ac c	Geo	Tim e	Re p
Bubble Barrier manufacturing							
<i>Bubble Barrier Compressor + Housing</i>							
Router, internet	1	P	market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	1
Charcoal	4.3E+01	kg/p	Market for l Cut-off U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Stainless steel	7.755E+02	kg/p	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Metal working	7.755E+02	kg/p	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aluminium cast alloy	6.40E+00	kg/p	market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Aluminium wrought alloy	1.36E+01	kg/p	market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Cast Iron	3.00E+01	kg/p	market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Copper Cathode	2.00E+01	kg/p	Copper production, cathode, solvent extraction and electrowinning process l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Injection moulding	2.75E+01	kg/p	Processing l Cut-off, U (RER)	3	3	3	2
Polystyrene	1.00E+01	kg/p	High impact, market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Printed Board Wiring	1.26E-01	kg/p	Pb containing, market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Printed Board Wiring	1.26E-01	kg/p	Pb free, market for l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Sheet aluminium rolling,	2.00E+01	kg/p	(RER) processing l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Sheet chromium steel rolling,	1.60E+01	kg/p	(RER) processing l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Sheet rolling, steel	4.00E+01	kg/p	(RER) processing l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Chromium steel	1.60E+01	kg/p	18/8, hot rolled (GLO) market for l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Steel	4.00E+01	kg/p	Low-alloyed, hot rolled (GLO) market for l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Synthetic Rubber	5.00E+00	kg/p	(GLO) market for l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Wire drawing, copper	9.00E+01	kg/p	(RER) processing l Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2

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Alkyd paint, white, without solvent, in 60% solution state	1.10E+01	kg/ρ	market for Alkyd paint, white, without solvent, in 60% solution state (RER)	3	2	1	2
Polyethylene, high density, granulate	2.15E+01	kg/ρ	market for, Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	1
Polystyrene, expandable	1.40E+01	kg/ρ	Market for, Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	1
Electronic components	2.115E+01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	7.43+00	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Refrigerant R134a	1.60E+00	kg/ρ	market for, Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	3	3	2
Reinforcing steel	6.00E+04	kg/ρ	market for reinforcing steel (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Sheet rolling	6.00E+04	kg/ρ	market for sheet rolling steel (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aluminium alloy	1.65E+01	kg/ρ	AlMg3 (GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Steel, low-alloyed	6.29E+00	kg/ρ	market for (GLO), Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Activated Carbon, granular	1.83+01	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for Activated Carbon, granular, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Electronics for Control Units	2.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for (GLO), Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Impact extrusion of Aluminium, strokes	3 1.65E+01	kg/ρ	market for (GLO), Cut-off, U	3	2	1	2
Metal working	3.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Polyvinylflouride	8.28E+00	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	2	1	2
Ferrite	7.00E+00	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	2	3	2
Epoxy Resin, liquid	2.20E+00	kg/ρ	(RER) market for epoxy resin, liquid, Cut-off, U	3	2	3	2
Air filter, in exhaust air valve	1	P	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Zinc	2.00E+00	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	3	3	1
Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer	1.00E+00	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	3	3	1
Internet Access Equipment	1	P	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	3	3	2
Catchment System							
Marine Grade 5083 Aluminium	1.891E+01	kg/ρ	market for (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Metal Working	1.891E+01	Kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Polyvinylchloride, suspension polymerised	5.00E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Tube Insulation, elastomere	9.94E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Cast Iron	7.32E+00	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Silicon Carbide	3.66E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Electronic components	3.66E-01	Kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1

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Electronic components	2.44E-01	Kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Bubble Hose Assembly							
Reinforcing steel	1.15E+03	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	2	1	1
Metal Working	1.15E+03	Kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Stainless steel	3.24E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Metal Working	3.24E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Concrete, normal	4.37E+03	m ³	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Synthetic Rubber	1.72E+03	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
PV System Manufacturing							
Photovoltaic cell	2.02E+02	m ²	Single-Si Wafer (GLO) market for	3	2	3	1
Brass	2.37E-01	kg/ρ	market for brass	3	2	2	1
Copper, cathode	3.07E+01	Kg/ρ	Copper production, cathode, solvent extraction and electrowinning process l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	2	2	1
Epoxy Resin, liquid	2.37E-02	Kg/ρ	(RER) market for epoxy resin, liquid, Cut-off, U	3	2	2	1
Nylon 6	2.73E+00	Kg/ρ	(RER) market for	3	2	2	1
Polycarbonate	2.37E-02	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	1
Polyethylene, high density, granulate	2.64E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	1
Polyvinylchloride	3.78E+00	Kg/ρ	Bulk polymerised (GLO) market for	3	2	2	1
Steel, low-alloyed	9.74E+00	Kg/ρ	Hot rolled, (GLO) market for	3	2	2	1
Wire drawing, copper	3.07E+01	Kg/ρ	(RER) processing	3	2	2	1
Zinc	4.74E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	1
Inverter 2.5KW	4.49E+00	P	(RER) production	3	2	3	2
Inverter 2.5KW	9.11E+00	P	(GLO) production	3	2	3	2
Photovoltaic mounting system	2.17E+02	m ²	For flat roof installation (GLO) market for	3	2	3	2
Propanol	1.76E+00	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Acetone, liquid	2.80E+00	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	3	2	2	2
Aluminium alloy	5.70E+02	Kg/ρ	AlMg3 (GLO) market for, Cut-off, U	3	2	2	2
Brazing solder, cadmium free	1.90E+00	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Copper, cathode	2.44E+01	Kg/ρ	Copper production, cathode, solvent extraction and electrowinning process l Cut-off, U (GLO)	3	2	2	2
Corrugated board box	2.76E+00	Kg/ρ	(CA-QC) market for	3	2	2	2
Corrugated board box	2.35E+02	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	3	2	2	2
Ethylvinylacetate, foil	2.17E+02	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Glass fibre reinforced plastic, polyamide, injection moulded	4.07E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Lubricating oil	3.48E-01	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	3	2	2	2

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Methanol	4.67E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Nickel, class 1	3.53E-02	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous	8.08E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Polyvinylflouride film	2.39E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Silicone product	2.64E+01	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	3	2	2	2
Solar glass, low iron	2.18E+03	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	7.18E+01	Kg/ρ	(BR) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	8.64E+00	Kg/ρ	(CA-CQ) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	1.43E+01	Kg/ρ	(CO) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	3.60E+02	Kg/ρ	(IN) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	9.37E+01	Kg/ρ	(PE) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	4.12E+03	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	3	2	2	2
Tap Water	2.67E+01	Kg/ρ	(ZA) market for	3	2	2	2
Tempering, flat glass	2.18E+03	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Vinyl Acetate	3.56E-01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
Wire drawing, copper	2.44E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	3	2	2	2
System transport to the site							
Transport	1.75E-04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO5 (RER) – 100 km	2	1	1	1
Transport	3.98E-04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 (RER) – 100 km	2	1	1	1
Installation of Bubble Barrier & Solar Panels							
Diesel, burned in building machine	1.94E+04	MJ	(GLO) market for	1	1	1	1
Electricity, low voltage	1.77E+00	kWh	(RER) market for	1	1	1	1
Bubble Barrier use and maintenance							
PV System Electricity Generation	5.00E+04	kWh	MAELSTROM	2	2	1	1
Electricity, low voltage	1.70E+05	kWh	(Europe without Switzerland) market group for	2	2	1	1
Tap Water	5.00E+02	kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	2	1	1
Lubricating Oil	1.76E+01	kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	2	3	1	1
Cleaning consumables, without water, in 13.6% solution state	5.00E+00	kg/ρ	(GLO) market for	2	3	1	2
System transport to the EoL							
Transport	1.75E-04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 300 km	2	1	1	1
Transport	7.08E+04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 300 km	2	1	1	1
Bubble Barrier dismantling and disposal							
Steel - recycle	1.51E+03	kg/ρ	recycling of steel and iron (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Steel - landfill	6.45E+02	kg/ρ	Market for scrap steel (EU without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1

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Plastic - recycle	1.15E+03	kg/ρ	recycling of mixed plastics (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Plastic - landfill	1.65E+03	kg/ρ	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, unsanitary landfill (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Plastic incineration	4.94E+02	kg/ρ	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Aluminium - recycle	8.66E+02	kg/ρ	recycling of aluminium (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Aluminium Landfill	3.71E+02	kg/ρ	treatment of waste aluminum, sanitary landfill (RoW)	2	1	1	1
Cable waste	2.70E+01	kg/ρ	market for used cable (GLO)	2	1	1	1
PVC - Recycling	8.8E+00	kg/ρ	Waste Treatment (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Waste Electric & Electronic Equipment	2.03E+01	Kg/ρ	Treatment of, shredding (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Scrap Copper	2.0E+01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1
Inert Waste	4.42E+03	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) treatment of waste, sanitary landfill	2	1	1	1
Hazardous Waste, for incineration	2.57E+01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1
Solar Panels dismantling and disposal							
Scrap Copper	3.51E-01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1
Steel - recycle	1.44E+00	kg/ρ	recycling of steel and iron (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Waste Electric wiring	6.13E+00	Kg/ρ	(RoW) market for	2	1	1	1
Waste polyethylene/polyp ropylene product	6.30E-03	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1
Waste polyvinylchloride product	1.53E+00	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) treatment of...for final disposal	2	1	1	1
PVC (Waste Treatment)	2.53E+00	Kg/ρ	(GLO) recycling of	2	1	1	1
Aluminium - recycle	2.56E+00	Kg/ρ	recycling of aluminium (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Scrap aluminium	5.4E-01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1
Steel - landfill	2.00E-01	kg/ρ	Market for scrap steel (EU without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1
Waste polystyrene	7.00E-03	Kg/ρ	(RER) Market group for	2	1	1	1
Waste glass	2.02E+00	Kg/ρ	(RER) Market group for	2	1	1	1
Packaging glass, white	1.70E+01	Kg/ρ	(GLO) Recycling of	2	1	1	1
Waste plastic, mixture	3.73E-01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market group for	2	1	1	1
Hazardous Waste, for incineration	3.50E-01	Kg/ρ	(Europe without Switzerland) market for	2	1	1	1

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6.1.2 Seabed cleaning platform

For the Seabed Cleaning Platform, all inventory data has been successfully collected. As mentioned above, the assessment of cleaning and segregation technologies, along with the equipment operation, considers manufacturing, installation, and equipment decommissioning. TECNALIA has provided the list of equipment and equipment components. Regarding the construction materials of the equipment and their quantities, estimates have been made by the partners responsible for equipment commissioning (TECNALIA) or by using the technical specifications of the equipment.

Given that in the MAELSTROM project, the equipment operates intermittently in campaigns lasting 2 or 4 weeks, aligned with the project's budget, estimations have been conducted to determine the information related to an actual equipment operating situation. The robot has been assumed to work 40 weeks per year, 5 days a week, 8 hours a day, totalling 1600 hours per year. Additionally, it has been estimated that approximately 100 kg can be collected for each robot descent, resulting in an approximate daily collection of 1000 kg. The plant's lifespan has been estimated to be 20 years.

A significant difference between the bubbly barrier and the platform operation time is that the barrier can operate continuously, as it does not require the presence of a person, unlike the platform.

The collected ML have been estimated to be treated as follows: approximately 35% is undergo various recycling processes for reuse, while 50% is sent to a sanitary landfill for proper disposal. The remaining 15% is treated through incineration, as part of the waste management process. The following tables show the inventory data gathered for general information (Table 5) and the equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling (Table 6).

Table 5 General information for the Seabed Cleaning Platform

General information	Value
Installation location	San Sebastian
Annual operation time	1600 h
Lifespan of the robot	20 years
Annual amount of ML collected	200.000 kg/year
Total plastic collected during the lifespan	4.000.000 kg

Table 6 Inventory data for the Seabed Cleaning Platform (equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Ac	Geo	Time	Rep
Robot manufacturing							
<i>Mobile platform</i>							
Unalloyed steel	5.29E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, unalloyed (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Paint	3.34E+01	kg/ρ	*Simulated	3	1	1	1
Stainless steel	1.96E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Lead	4.40E+02	kg/ρ	market for lead (GLO)	3	2	1	1
High density polyethylene (HDPE)	4.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for polyethylene, high density, granulate (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Metal working	1.96E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	5.29E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Injection (for plastic)	4.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
<i>Main capsule</i>							
Polymethyl methacrylate	1.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for polymethyl methacrylate, beads (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	1.05E+00	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	4.50E-01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Injection (for plastic)	1.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
<i>Smart Camera capsule</i>							
Polymethyl methacrylate	1.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for polymethyl methacrylate, beads (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	7.00E-01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Electronic components	3.00E-01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Injection (for plastic)	1.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
<i>Supporting structures</i>							
Unalloyed steel	3.38E+03	kg/ρ	market for steel, unalloyed (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Stainless steel	8.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Bronze	4.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for bronze (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Reinforcing steel	2.52E+02	kg/ρ	market for reinforcing steel (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Polycarbonate	2.40E+01	kg/ρ	market for polycarbonate (GLO)	3	2	1	1

HDPE	1.00E+00	kg/p	market for polyethylene, high density, granulate (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Metal working	8.00E+00	kg/p	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	3.64E+03	kg/p	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Injection plastic) (for	2.50E+01	kg/p	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Casting bronze	4.00E+00	kg/p	market for casting, bronze (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Sensors							
Stainless steel	1.60E+00	kg/p	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	2.18E+00	kg/p	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Electronic components	9.14E-01	kg/p	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	1.60E+00	kg/p	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Floating platform							
Reinforcing steel	6.00E+04	kg/p	market for reinforcing steel (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Sheet rolling	6.00E+04	kg/p	market for sheet rolling, steel (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aspiration system							
Stainless steel	5.65E-02	kg/p	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Polyvinylchloride (PVC)	3.29E+00	kg/p	market for polyvinylchloride, suspension polymerised (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Extrusion	3.29E+00	kg/p	market for extrusion, plastic pipes (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Power generator							
Generator	1.74E+03	kg/p	market for generator, 200kW electrical (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Control room							
Aluminium	1.00E+02	kg/p	market for aluminium alloy, metal matrix composite (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Stainless steel	5.50E+02	kg/p	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Electronic components	1.05E+02	kg/p	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	2
Electronic components	4.50E+01	kg/p	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	2
Laptop	4.00E+00	p/p	market for computer, laptop (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Sheet rolling	4.00E+02	kg/p	market for sheet rolling, aluminium (GLO)	3	2	1	2

Sheet rolling	2.50E+02	kg/ρ	market for sheet rolling, steel (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Auxiliary Container							
Aluminium	1.50E+02	kg/ρ	market for aluminium alloy, metal matrix composite (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Stainless steel	6.00E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Sheet rolling	1.50E+02	kg/ρ	market for sheet rolling, aluminium (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Sheet rolling	6.00E+02	kg/ρ	market for sheet rolling, steel (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Cables							
Stainless steel	2.68E+01	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Cable	1.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for cable, unspecified (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Robot transport to the site							
Transport	2.36E+04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 100 km	2	1	1	1
Robot Installation							
Crane operation	7.00E+02	h/ρ	market for machine operation, diesel, < 18.64 kW, steady-state (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Generator operation	1.00E+01	h/ρ	market for machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, generators (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Robot use and maintenance							
Generator operation	3.20E+04	h/ρ	market for machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, generators (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Lubricating oil	1.00E+02	kg/ρ	market for lubricating oil (RER)	2	1	1	1
Paint	2.88E+01	kg/ρ	*Simulated	2	1	1	1
Diesel	3.20E+05	kg/ρ	market for diesel (Europe without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1
Waste incineration	- 6.00E+05	kg/ρ	market for municipal solid waste, incineration (ES)	3	2	1	1
Waste - landfill	2.00E+06	kg/ρ	Inert waste, sanitary landfill (Europe without Switzerland)	3	2	1	1
Waste - recycle	1.40E+06	kg/ρ		3	2	1	1
Robot transport to the EoL							
Transport	7.08E+04	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 300 km	2	1	1	1
Robot dismantling and disposal							
Steel - recycle	4.70E+04	kg/ρ	recycling of steel and iron (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Steel - landfill	2.01E+04	kg/ρ	treatment of scrap steel, inert material landfill (RER)	2	1	1	1
Plastic - recycle	1.24E+01	kg/ρ	recycling of mixed plastics (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Plastic - landfill	1.76E+01	kg/ρ	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, unsanitary landfill (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Plastic incineration	- 5.29E+00	kg/ρ	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration (GLO)	2	1	1	1

Electronic waste	1.90E+03	kg/ρ	market for waste electric and electronic equipment (GLO)	2	1	1	1	
Aluminium – recycle	1.75E+02	kg/ρ	recycling of aluminium (GLO)	2	1	1	1	
Aluminium Landfill	-	7.50E+01	kg/ρ	treatment of waste aluminium, sanitary landfill (RoW)	2	1	1	1
Cable waste	1.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for used cable (GLO)	2	1	1	1	
Laptop waste	1.00E+01	kg/ρ	market for used laptop computer (GLO)	2	1	1	1	

6.2 Segregation and recycling technologies

6.2.1 AI-driven Robotic system

For the AI-powered robotic system, TECNALIA has provided all inventory data necessary to conduct this LCA. As in the case of the cleaning process, the segregation process includes manufacturing, use, and dismantling of the equipment. Due to insufficient available data, the installation stage has been omitted from the study. Estimates have been made to determine the construction materials of the equipment and their quantities, and the technical specifications of the equipment have been used.

In this case, the segregation process has been assumed to work 50 weeks per year, 5 days a week, 8 hours a day, totalling 2000 hours per year. Certain approximations and estimations have been employed in this scenario to gauge the potential quantity of segregated waste. Specifically, it has been assumed that 60 items per minute can undergo segregation, with an estimated weight of 0.5 kg per item. Based on these assumptions, calculations indicate that approximately 1800 kg per hour of waste can be segregated. This waste may include ML as well as other types of waste. However, for this study, it has been considered that the segregated waste is only ML. The plant's lifespan has been concluded to be 15 years.

As the technologies under consideration in the project particularly target specific types of ML, an assumption has been made that the 50% of the waste could be effectively managed using the recycling technologies developed in the MAELSTROM project. The remaining 50% has been allocated as follows: 35% has been presumed to be recyclable using alternative technologies, 10.05% has been designated for sanitary landfill, and the remaining 4.5% has been earmarked for treatment via incineration. It is worth mentioning that the waste treated through MAELSTROM's recycling processes and other waste amenable to various recycling methods have been excluded from the system boundaries for the segregation processes.

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The following tables show the inventory data gathered for general information (Table 7) and the equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling (

Table 8).

Table 7 General information for the AI-driven Robotic system

General information	Value
Installation location	San Sebastian
Annual operation time	2000 h
Lifespan of the robot	15 years
Annual amount of ML sorted	3.600.000 kg/year
Total plastic collected during the lifespan	54.000.000 kg

Table 8 Inventory data for the AI-driven Robotic system (equipment's manufacture, installation, use and dismantling)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Ac	Geo	Time	Rep
Robot manufacturing							
<i>Perception and AI classification unit</i>							
Aluminium	1.00E+02	kg/ρ	market for aluminium alloy, metal matrix composite (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Copper	9.37E-01	kg/ρ	market for copper, cathode (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Stainless steel	2.58E+01	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Glass	4.40E+02	kg/ρ	market for flat glass, uncoated (RER)	3	2	1	1
HDPE	7.50E+00	kg/ρ	market for polyethylene, high density, granulate (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Rubber	1.29E-01	kg/ρ	market for synthetic rubber (GLO)	3	3	2	1
Paint	1.07E+00	kg/ρ	*Simulated	1	1	1	1
Steel low alloy	2.63E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, low-alloyed (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	1.05E+00	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	4.50E-01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Laptop	1.00E+01	ρ/ρ	market for computer, laptop (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Metal working	2.58E+01	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel	3	2	1	2

			product manufacturing (GLO)				
Metal working	2.63E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Injection (for plastic)	7.63E+00	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aluminium extrusion	1.00E+02	kg/ρ	market for impact extrusion of aluminium, 3 strokes (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Wire drawing (copper)	9.37E-01	kg/ρ	market for wire drawing, copper (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Robot unit							
Aluminium	7.85E+01	kg/ρ	market for aluminium alloy, metal matrix composite (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Steel low alloy	6.76E+02	kg/ρ	market for steel, low-alloyed (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Stainless steel	1.96E+01	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	3.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Electronic components	1.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Paint	3.00E+00	kg/ρ	*Simulated	1	1	1	1
Coating powder	1.00E+00	kg/ρ	market for coating powder (GLO) - changing with polystyrene with polyurethane	3	2	1	1
Polycarbonate	3.40E+01	kg/ρ	market for polycarbonate (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Nitrile butadiene rubber	1.00E-02	kg/ρ	market for nitrile-compound (GLO)	3	2	1	1
Cable	1.76E+01	kg/ρ	market for cable, unspecified (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Carbon fibre reinforced plastic	1.20E+00	kg/ρ	market for carbon fibre reinforced plastic, injection moulded (GLO)	1	1	1	1
Injection (for plastic)	1.00E-02	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	1.96E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	6.76E+02	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aluminium extrusion	3.00E-01	kg/ρ	market for impact extrusion of aluminium, 3 strokes (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Plastic extrusion	3.40E+01	kg/ρ	market for extrusion of plastic sheets and thermoforming, inline (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Conveyor belts							
Stainless steel	3.33E+01	kg/ρ	market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Aluminium	4.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for aluminium alloy, metal matrix composite (GLO)	2	1	1	1

Steel low alloy	3.16E+04	kg/ρ	market for steel, low-alloyed (GLO)	2	1	1	1
PVC	3.60E+01	kg/ρ	market for polyvinylchloride, suspension polymerised (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Nitrile butadiene rubber	1.20E+00	kg/ρ	market for nitrile-compound (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Cable	1.26E+01	kg/ρ	market for cable, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Lubricating oil	3.00E-01	kg/ρ	market for lubricating oil (RER)	2	1	1	1
Electronic components	1.06E+01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, passive, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Electronic components	1.86E+01	kg/ρ	market for electronic component, active, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Metal working	3.33E+01	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Metal working	3.16E+04	kg/ρ	market for metal working, average for steel product manufacturing (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Injection (for plastic)	1.20E+00	kg/ρ	market for injection moulding (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Aluminium extrusion	4.50E+01	kg/ρ	market for impact extrusion of aluminium, 3 strokes (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Plastic extrusion	3.60E+01	kg/ρ	market for extrusion of plastic sheets and thermoforming, inline (GLO)	3	2	1	2
Robot transport to the site							
Transport	3.30E+03	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 100 km	2	1	1	1
Robot use and maintenance							
Electricity	6.67E+01	kWh/ρ	market for electricity, low voltage (Europe without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1
Waste incineration	2.43E+06	kg/ρ	market for municipal solid waste, incineration (ES)	3	2	1	1
Waste - landfill	6.67E+06	kg/ρ	Inert waste, sanitary landfill (Europe without Switzerland)	3	2	1	1
Waste - recycle	4.59E+07	kg/ρ	-	3	2	1	1
Robot transport to the EoL							
Transport	9.89E+03	tkm/ρ	market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 (RER) – 300 km	2	1	1	1
Robot dismantling and disposal							
Steel - recycle	2.28E+04	kg/ρ	recycling of steel and iron (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Steel - landfill	9.79E+03	kg/ρ	treatment of scrap steel, inert material landfill (RER)	2	1	1	1
Plastic - recycle	1.54E+01	kg/ρ	recycling of mixed plastics (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Plastic - landfill	2.20E+01	kg/ρ	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, unsanitary landfill (GLO)	2	1	1	1

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Plastic incineration	-	6.61E+00	kg/p	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration (GLO)	2	1	1	1
PVC - recycle		3.60E+01	kg/p	recycling of PVC (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Glass waste		1.63E+00	kg/p	Waste glass (Europe without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1
Electronic waste		4.92E+01	kg/p	market for waste electric and electronic equipment (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Aluminium - recycle		9.98E+01	kg/p	recycling of aluminium (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Aluminium Landfill	-	4.28E+01	kg/p	treatment of waste aluminium, sanitary landfill (RoW)	2	1	1	1
Copper - waste		9.32E-01	kg/p	market for municipal incineration scrap (Europe without Switzerland)	2	1	1	1
Cable waste		3.02E+01	kg/p	market for used cable (GLO)	2	1	1	1
Laptop waste		2.50E+00	kg/p	market for used laptop computer (GLO)	2	1	1	1

6.2.2 Thermoplastic recycling (additivation and shredding)

In the MAESLTROM project, the treatment of 1 kg of dry ML using recycling technologies has been established as FU. As mentioned, in the segregation process, the waste is classified depending on its composition and characteristics. In this way, it can be determined which recycling process should be used for each type of waste. In this sense, Table 9 presents the inventory data for the thermoplastic recycling process (only equipment's use):

Table 9 Inventory data for the thermoplastic recycling process (only equipment's use)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Acc	Geo	Time	Rep
Electricity	9.9E-01	kWh/kg	Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Water	8E+00	l/kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for tap water Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Glass fibre	2.5E-01	Kg/kg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for glass fibre Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Wastewater	8E+00	l/kg	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Transport	1.38E-3	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RER} transport, freight, lorry, all sizes, EURO6 to generic market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	2	1	1	1

As observed, the water used for cleaning the buoys is discharged through the stormwater drainage system.

Regarding the product output, in the extrusion process, all material introduced into the equipment is fully recovered, and the material that cannot be extruded (extrusion lumps) or is injected but does not form part of the test specimen (sprue) can be reused.

6.2.3 Hard-to-recycle plastics (thermal press molding)

In the context of the hard-to-recycle plastics process, comprehensive inventory data has been effectively amassed, and Gees Recycling has conducted the LCA analysis. Table 10 Inventory data for the hard-to-recycle process (only equipment's use):

Table 10 Inventory data for the hard-to-recycle process (only equipment's use)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Acc	Geo	Time	Rep
Electricity	Sensitive data	kWh/kg	Electricity, low voltage {IT} market for Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Water	Sensitive data	l/kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Bonding Agent	Sensitive data	Kg/kg	Polyurethane adhesive {GLO} polyurethane adhesive production Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1
Coloring Oxides	Sensitive data	Kg/kg	Polyurethane adhesive {GLO} polyurethane adhesive production Cut-off, U	1	1	1	1

The inventory data processing has been based on the Ecoinvent database (cut-off method). The following exclusion criteria have been applied:

- Production of machinery, buildings, and other capital goods
- Staff business travel
- Employee commuting
- Waste production
- Emissions into the atmosphere (considered negligible).

These criteria have been established to streamline the analysis by focusing on the most relevant aspects and minimizing the inclusion of negligible or less impactful elements.

Gees Recycling has been founded in Pordenone (PN – Italy) in 2010. In collaboration with AREA, a system for recycling materials in polyesters, ABS, rigid thermosetting foams, and fibre-reinforced composites, which are still destined for landfills today, has been designed and patented. The waste materials that have been recycled come from the sanitary ware sector (e.g., hydromassage tubs), manufacturing (fibreglass products), wind power, companies producing boats, campers, agricultural vehicles, etc. Efforts have been made to reduce CO₂ emissions with a recycling process of fibre-reinforced composites and rigid foams with a thermosetting matrix, otherwise destined for landfill. After five years of research and development, the international patent has been obtained and industrial production has begun in the new headquarters in Aviano. With a non-polluting mechanical process, the waste has been sent for recovery in the form of granulates.

The following non-hazardous waste recovery activities have been carried out at the plant in question, described in the relevant paragraphs of annex 1, sub-annex 1 of Ministerial Decree 05/02/1998:

1. Type 6.1 of Ministerial Decree 02/05/1998: plastic waste; used plastic packaging including containers for liquids, except for containers for pesticides and medical-surgical devices.
 - Characteristics: plastic materials, including sheets and bags, tubes for yarn cones, of various compositions and shapes with the possible presence of other types of waste.
 - Origin: separate waste collection, selection from MSW or RA; industrial, artisanal, commercial, and agricultural activities; construction and demolition activities.
 - Recovery activities: EER Codes [020104], [150102], [170203], [191204], [200139] - placed in reserve [R13] for the production of secondary raw materials for the plastics industry, by removing the foreign substances (if present), treatment to obtain plastic materials compliant with the specifications of the Uniplast - Uni 10667 standards (In the absence of a specific standard of the 10667 series, the classification can be carried out, in agreement between the parties, taking inspiration from the methodologies cited in the existing standards of the series. The parties must in any case declare the treatments carried out and determine the presence of any impurities or unwanted materials) and to produce plastic products in the forms usually marketed [R3]. Annual quantity: 275 t. EER codes [020104], [150102], [170203], [191204], [200139] - put into reserve [R13]. Annual quantity: 275 t.

2. Type 6.2 of Ministerial Decree 02/05/1998: scraps, waste, dust and waste of plastic materials and synthetic fibres.
 - Characteristics: granules, shavings, clippings, powders, non-standard products, etc. Possible presence of other polymers, fillers, pigments, additives, Pb < 3%, KOH < 0.3%, Cd < 0.3%.
 - Origin: industry, production or transformation of plastic materials and synthetic fibres, waste battery recovery systems, car demolition activity authorized pursuant to Legislative Decree 5 February 1997, n. 22 and subsequent amendments and additions, car repair and automotive industry activities, other recovery activities of other equipment and artefacts; construction and demolition activities.
 - Recovery activities: EER Codes [070213], [120105], [160119], [160216], [160306], [170203] - placed in reserve [R13] for the production of secondary raw materials for the plastics industry, by removing foreign substances (if present), treatment to obtain plastic materials compliant with Uniplast - Uni 10667 specifications (In the absence of a specific standard of the 10667 series, the classification can be carried out, in agreement between the parties, taking inspiration from the methodologies cited in the existing standards of the series. The parties must in any case declare the treatments carried out and determine the presence of any impurities or unwanted materials) and to produce plastic products in the forms usually marketed [R3]. Annual quantity: 1,825 t. EER codes [070213], [120105], [160119], [160216], [160306], [170203] - put into reserve [R13]. Annual quantity: 1,825 t. Maximum (overall) instantaneous storable quantity of waste has been equal to: 630 t.

Through a high-pressure hot moulding process, the granulate has been transformed into panels, using a percentage of virgin raw materials. The phases of the production process can be the following (Figure 10): screening, mixing, printing, squaring and calibration and cutting and finishing.

Figure 10 Hard-to-recycle process: diagram.

All the waste obtained from the sampling related to the order and the scrap obtained from the cutting and finishing of the slabs made in GEES RECYCLING with "End of Waste - EoW" material have been sent for rework within the same production cycle. The waste and scrap have been sent first for shredding and then grinding to obtain a granulate suitable for introduction into the mixing phase, which will lead to the production of new slabs. The traceability of the materials used in the creation of the "EoW" product, the EoW RZC xx fillers, the by-product, and the artefacts has been guaranteed by establishing and implementing a traceability plan for the materials and flows within the recovery process in the plant and the production process, thanks to the I-SMART corporate waste management software. The following diagram illustrates the production process of GEES Recycling Srl (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Production process of GEES Recycling Srl.

6.2.4 Temperature pyrolysis

In the context of the pyrolysis procedure, comprehensive inventory data has been effectively amassed, and VIEGAND MAAGØE has conducted the LCA analysis. This consultancy entity has been subcontracted by MAKEEN ENERGY.

Table 11 shows the composition of the ML that has been employed in the pyrolysis process.

Table 11 ML composition (raw material in the pyrolysis process)

Plastic type	Content
Polypropylene (PP):	0.1 %
HDPE	87.4%
Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE):	11.7 %
Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)	0.1 %
Styrene	0.1 %
Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA)	0.1 %
Miscellaneous	0.3 %

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The operational sequence involves the treatment of 1 kg of dry ML in MAKEEN, where it is subjected to a grinding process. Subsequently, the crushed material is subjected to the pyrolysis process as part of the recycling technologies used within the project.

In contrast to the procedures involved in cleaning and segregation, the evaluation of recycling processes, including pyrolysis, has exclusively encompassed considerations related to the utilization and maintenance of equipment. Notably, this assessment has omitted factors associated with the equipment's manufacturing, installation, and dismantling.

Furthermore, the analysis carried out for the pyrolysis process does not cover the initial processes that involve the collection, cleaning, classification and crushing of marine debris, nor does it extend to the subsequent processes that involve the use of pyrolysis products as fuel. Since all outputs have potential value for further processing into fuel, plastic production, fertilizer, or heat production, they have been intentionally omitted from the modelling within this system.

However, the only residual flow from the process has been degassing condensate, an aqueous solution containing 1 and 5% organic material composed mainly of short-chain carbon compounds. The presence of other substances in small quantities depends on the specific plastic waste that is introduced into the process. For this assessment, the ML sample from the MAELSTROM project that MAKEEN received in July 2022 has served as the basis for the LCA, which reveals the absence of additional compounds in the degassing condensate.

The energy contribution for the process has been exclusively from electricity. Nitrogen has been used to establish an inert environment within the reactors to control the process, and compressed air has been employed to introduce plastic into the pyrolysis chamber. Based on the system boundaries, the LCI has been modelled and is presented in Table 12. It has been decided to exclude specific LCI data from the process due to its sensitivity. This measure is taken to maintain confidentiality and safeguard private information related to the experimental procedures.

Table 12 Inventory data for the pyrolysis process (only equipment's use)

Environmental aspect	Value	Unit	LCI dataset	Data quality assessment			
				Ac c	Geo	Tim e	Re p
Operation of pyrolysis							
Nitrogen	Sensitive data	m ³ /kg ML	market for nitrogen, liquid (RER)	1	1	1	1
Compressed air	Sensitive data	m ³ /kg ML	compressed air production, 600 kPa gauge, >30kW, average generation (RER)	1	1	1	1
Electricity	Sensitive data	Wh/kg ML	market group for electricity, medium voltage (RER)	1	1	1	1
Degas condensate waste	- 2.75E-02	m ³ /kg ML	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment (Europe without Switzerland)	2	1	1	2
Transport of raw material	1.38E-03	tkm/kg ML	transport, freight, lorry, all sizes, EURO6 to generic market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified (GLO)	2	1	1	1

7 Life cycle impact assessment

The Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) phase aims at analysing the data collected during the LCI phase and calculating the potential environmental impacts associated with the inputs and outputs. To calculate the impacts, the LCIA method that has been chosen is the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) method. In addition, the impact categories that have been selected to monitor the environmental performance of MAELSTROM technologies are listed below (Table 13) (European Commission, 2021):

- **Acidification (AC):** is generated by pollutants such as SO₂ and NO_x that react with steam, forming acids. The acids reach the earth, negatively affecting soil, water, fauna, and flora. The NH₃, NO, NO₂, NO_x and SO₂ emissions are responsible for environmental damage.
- **Climate change, total (GW):** represents the amount of additional radiative forcing integrated in time (20, 100 or 1,000 years). The causes of this impact are greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, CFC, HCFC, HFC, chlorocarbons, hydrochlorocarbons, bromocarbons, hydrobromocarbons, halons, halogenated alcohols, and others). This effect negatively influences human health and the environment, causing, among others, global average air temperature changes, which causes devastating damage to ecosystems.
- **Ecotoxicity, freshwater (ETX):** is related to the risks and consequences generated by the presence of chemicals released into the environment.

- **Particulate matter (PM):** accounts for the adverse health effects on human health caused by emissions of PM and its precursors (NO_x, SO_x, NH₃).
- **Eutrophication (EP):** Nutrients from sewage outfalls and fertilized farmland accelerate the growth of algae and other vegetation in the water. The degradation of organic material consumes oxygen resulting in oxygen deficiency and, in some cases, fish death. Eutrophication translates the quantity of substances emitted into a common measure expressed as the oxygen required for the degradation of dead biomass. Three EF impact categories are used: Eutrophication - terrestrial (ET), Eutrophication - freshwater (EF), and Eutrophication - marine (EM).
- **Human toxicity - cancer (HTc):** causes adverse health effects in humans caused by ingesting toxic substances through inhalation of air, ingestion of food/water, and penetration through the skin to the extent that they are related to cancer.
- **Human toxicity - non-cancer (HTnc):** accounts for the adverse health effects on human beings caused by the intake of toxins as they are related to non-cancer impacts not caused by PM/respiratory inorganics or ionizing radiation.
- **Land use (LU):** impact category related to the use (occupation) and conversion (transformation) of land area by activities such as agriculture, forestry, roads, housing, mining, etc. Land occupation considers the amount of area involved and the duration of its occupation.
- **Resource use, fossils (ADff):** is related to using non-renewable abiotic natural resources. ADff only includes the extraction of different fossil natural resources (e.g., natural gas, coal, oil).
- **Resource use, minerals, and metals (ADe):** is related to the use of non-renewable abiotic natural resources. In the case of ADe, only the extraction of minerals and metals is considered.
- **Water use (WU):** represents the amount of available water remaining per area in a watershed after the demand from humans and aquatic ecosystems was met. This impact category assesses the potential for water deprivation, whether for humans or ecosystems, based on the assumption that the less water available per area, the more likely it is that another user will be deprived.
- **Cumulative energy demand (CED):** The sum of the primary energy demand associated with the life cycle of a product (i.e., covering production, manufacture, use and disposal). It is divided into 2 categories: non-renewable

energy (fossil, nuclear and biomass) and renewable energy (biomass, wind, solar, geothermal and water).

Table 13 Impact categories in the EF 3.1 and CED method

Impact Category	Unit	Abbreviation
Acidification	mol H ⁺ eq	AC
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	GW
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	ETX
Particulate matter	disease inc.	PM
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	EM
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	EF
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	ET
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	HTc
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	HTnc
Land use	Pt	LU
Resource use, fossils	MJ	ADff
Resource use, minerals, and metals	kg Sb eq	ADe
Water use	m ³ depriv.	WU
Non-renewable, fossil	MJ	
Non-renewable, nuclear	MJ	CED-nr
Non-renewable, biomass	MJ	
Renewable, biomass	MJ	
Renewable, wind, solar, geothermal	MJ	CED-r
Renewable, water	MJ	

8 Life cycle assessment results

Under SimaPro³, two different approaches can be followed (Schaubroeck et al., 2021). Attributional, assigns elementary flows and potential environmental impacts to a specific product system, typically as an account of the history of the product. Consequential, studies the environmental consequences of possible (future) changes between alternative product systems.

³ SimaPro is one of the leading sustainability and life cycle assessment software.

Figure 12 Difference between attributional and consequential LCA (Schaubroeck et al., 2021)

According to the figure, the attributional approach is based on the assessment of the whole life cycle of a product, what is precisely of interest in this study. The consequential approach does not consider the life cycle but identifies the (future) consequences for the market after the product has been manufactured. Particularly, it determines the (future) effects using marginal data (Finnveden & Potting, 2014) (EUCAR, 2020). This means that only those providers that are directly affected by the production process under study are included, omitting the existence of other providers that can be indirectly affected.

In addition, the attributional approach is the most widely employed method among the LCA community, with more than 95% of all LCAs performed under this approach (Cherubini & Strømman, 2011; Oliver et al., 2022). The same approach (either attributional or consequential) must be followed to compare different systems.

Two different methods exist within the attributional approach: the cut-off and the Allocation at the point of substitution (APOS) allocation methods. In the former, the

responsibility for the product's end of life (EoL) route is directly transferred to the producer (commonly known as the 'polluter pays' principle). Thus, the use of secondary materials is incentivized. In the latter, the impact of an activity that produces waste and its treatment is shared between all the products, the products being understood as those generated during the first cycle but also in the successive cycles because of a recycling or reuse process. This fosters the improvement of waste treatments to produce better products. Therefore, considering all of this, the cut-off allocation method will be followed in this analysis.

On the other hand, Ecoinvent includes both market processes and transformation processes in its database for use in LCA studies. Market processes represent the inputs and outputs of product markets at a national, regional, or global level and may include inputs from production and transportation processes in one or more countries. In the absence of specific supplier information, market processes may be used instead. On the other hand, transformation processes encompass all inputs necessary for producing a product or service, except for inputs from transportation processes and associated emissions and resource extractions. Considering that the average transportation of raw materials will be included in this analysis, the LCA analysis will consider the transformation processes. However, market processes may be chosen if information on the origin of any raw materials is unavailable.

The MAELSTROM project aims at assessing the environmental impacts of the MAELSTROM processes throughout their life cycle to identify the main hotspots. For this reason, an attributional approach will be followed, using transformation processes and the cut-off allocation method.

This section summarizes the quantification and evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with the MAELSTROM cleaning and recycling processes based on the LCA created with the SimaPro v9.2 software.

The environmental results are presented in two main parts:

- Results for cleaning technologies: Bubble barrier and Seabed cleaning platform.

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- Results for segregation and recycling technologies: AI-driven robotic system (segregation) and Thermoplastic recycling, Hard-to-recycle plastic and pyrolysis (recycling).

The environmental impact assessment has examined each technology individually to identify the main hotspots associated with each MAELSTROM technology. A comprehensive LCA analysis encompassing the entire chain of ML elimination has not been conducted, as the cleaning and segregation processes have been currently operating at a pilot/industrial scale, while the recycling processes have been at a laboratory scale. Additionally, given the disparity in the production scales, capital goods have not been considered, as they are all previously acquired and given their laboratory scale, would be inefficient.

8.1 Cleaning technologies

8.1.1 Bubble Barrier

This section presents the environmental impacts arising from ML cleaning using the Bubble Barrier cleaning technology, encompassing all stages within the system's boundaries: manufacturing, installation, utilization, and EoL management of the equipment (Figure 13 and Table 14). Conducting this type of analysis enables the identification of the stage that predominantly contributes to environmental impact, directing efforts towards process optimization and enhancing overall environmental performance.

Figure 13 Impact analysis for the Bubble Barrier & solar panels considering all the stages involved in the technology

Table 14 Impact analysis for different stages of the Bubble Barrier & solar panels: characterization results for each impact category

Impact category	Unit	Total	Manufacturing of Bubble Barrier	Transportation	Installation	Operation & Maintenance	Transportation2	End-of-Life Complete System
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	3.58E-03	1.56E-03	2.64E-07	6.04E-06	2.01E-03	2.64E-07	3.27E-07
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	8.00E-01	4.28E-01	6.61E-05	5.79E-04	3.71E-01	6.61E-05	3.80E-04
ETX	CTUe	1.12E+01	5.89E+00	7.63E-04	4.54E-03	5.18E+00	7.63E-04	7.84E-02
PM	disease inc.	2.37E-08	1.71E-08	4.57E-12	1.60E-10	6.40E-09	4.57E-12	1.02E-11
EM	kg N eq	8.31E-04	4.75E-04	8.10E-08	2.68E-06	3.52E-04	8.10E-08	1.39E-06
EF	kg P eq	4.26E-04	6.24E-05	4.44E-09	1.75E-08	3.64E-04	4.44E-09	1.40E-08
ET	mol N eq	8.43E-03	5.28E-03	8.84E-07	2.93E-05	3.12E-03	8.84E-07	1.24E-06
HTc	CTUh	3.65E-10	2.16E-10	2.72E-14	2.23E-13	1.50E-10	2.72E-14	1.45E-13
HTnc	CTUh	7.90E-09	3.92E-09	7.75E-13	3.22E-12	3.97E-09	7.75E-13	1.69E-12
LU	Pt	4.98E+00	3.67E+00	6.88E-04	1.03E-03	1.31E+00	6.88E-04	1.28E-03
ADff	MJ	1.06E+01	3.05E+00	9.99E-04	7.95E-03	7.55E+00	9.99E-04	7.15E-04
ADe	kg Sb eq	7.37E-06	3.74E-06	2.38E-10	2.34E-10	3.64E-06	2.38E-10	1.43E-10
WU	m ³ depriv.	2.02E-01	1.17E-01	2.84E-06	1.15E-05	8.49E-02	2.84E-06	3.85E-05
CED-nr	MJ	1.12E+01	3.24E+00	1.06E-03	8.44E-03	7.93E+00	1.06E-03	7.60E-04
CED-r	MJ	2.47E+00	1.59E-01	1.35E-05	4.12E-05	2.31E+00	1.35E-05	2.03E-05

MAELSTROM Figure 14 shows the network diagram considering the single score method.

Figure 14 Impact analysis for the Bubble Barrier & solar panels considering the network diagram (single score method)

The results have shown that the stage that causes the most harm to the environment is the operation and maintenance of the equipment. The impact of this stage constitutes roughly 59.7% of the total impact of the system, followed by equipment manufacturing with 40%. The remaining stages exhibit significantly lower environmental impacts, ranging from 0.2% to 0.01% in comparison.

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category generated the highest environmental impact, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 15). Weighting ranks or quantifies the contribution of an impact category to the overall impact, determining how significant an impact category is compared to other impact categories.

Figure 15 Impact analysis for the Bubble Barrier & solar panels considering all the stages involved in the technology: weighting

The results of Figure 15 have highlighted four main categories with highest values: GW, ADff, ADe and EF. The results indicated that the high value in GW is closely related to the generation of CO₂, emissions mainly, followed by methane emissions. These emissions are linked to the use of the compressor and the production (background processes) of concrete during the manufacturing stage of the equipment, specifically the bubble hose assembly.

In the case of ADff, this category is affected by the use of uranium, coal, crude oil, and natural gas which are raw materials used for electricity generation (background processes) (Shafiee & Topal, 2009). These resources are essential for the generation of energy and operation of machinery, which causes their depletion.

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On the other hand, in ADe the impact is related to the use of metals such as gold, tellurium and silver, which are used to produce active electronic components (Takayoshi Ueno et al., 1999). The extraction and processing of these metals entails an intense demand for energy and resources, contributing significantly to the depletion of these non-renewable resources (Richards, 2006).

Regarding EF, it has been observed that the impact is associated with phosphate emissions to freshwater water bodies during the use of the Bubble Barrier, as well as the manufacturing stage. These emissions come primarily from the combustion of fossil fuels and other industrial processes, contributing to the pollution of water bodies, leading to eutrophication. It is important to note that the functioning of the Bubble Barrier does not directly emit phosphate into freshwater bodies, but rather, it's a byproduct of electricity generated and later consumed by the Bubble Barrier. Furthermore, apart from the system in Portugal, all active Bubble Barriers use renewable energy, so the impact found in this study specifically relates to a situation where grid energy is not renewable.

The impact in these categories is closely related to the use of natural resources, the generation of polluting emissions and the production of essential components in the manufacturing and operation of equipment. Identifying these connections is crucial to implement effective mitigation measures and promoting more sustainable practices in the operations.

Figure 16 and Table 15 offer a more detailed view of the environmental repercussions of using and maintaining the equipment. This way of representing the results offers the possibility to show all the inputs and outputs associated to this stage, providing a comprehensive view of its environmental footprint.

Figure 16 Environmental impacts of the Bubble Barrier & solar panels operation and maintenance stage: input/output analysis

Table 15 Environmental impacts of Bubble Barrier & solar panels use and maintenance stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Complete PV System/Solar Electricity Production	Electricity, low voltage	Tap water	Lubricating oil	Cleaning consumables
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	2.01E-03	5.82E-05	1.95E-03	1.87E-09	8.63E-07	5.53E-07
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	3.71E-01	1.07E-02	3.60E-01	3.44E-07	1.24E-04	9.13E-05
ETX	CTUe	5.18E+00	4.65E-01	4.70E+00	5.77E-06	3.75E-03	3.31E-03
PM	disease inc.	6.40E-09	6.44E-10	5.75E-09	1.61E-14	6.22E-12	5.66E-12
EM	kg N eq	3.52E-04	1.26E-05	3.39E-04	3.69E-10	1.39E-07	1.73E-07
EF	kg P eq	3.64E-04	6.98E-06	3.57E-04	2.48E-10	3.20E-08	2.84E-08
ET	mol N eq	3.12E-03	1.25E-04	2.99E-03	3.47E-09	1.49E-06	1.26E-06
HTc	CTUh	1.50E-10	9.45E-12	1.40E-10	1.39E-15	8.30E-14	8.12E-14
HTnc	CTUh	3.97E-09	2.70E-10	3.70E-09	1.92E-14	1.73E-12	1.87E-12
LU	Pt	1.31E+00	3.77E-02	1.27E+00	1.39E-06	7.71E-04	1.14E-03
Adff	MJ	7.55E+00	1.33E-01	7.41E+00	5.84E-06	5.43E-03	1.34E-03
Ade	kg Sb eq	3.64E-06	4.15E-07	3.22E-06	1.61E-12	1.78E-09	1.26E-09
WU	m ³ depriv.	8.49E-02	7.48E-03	7.73E-02	4.31E-05	3.43E-05	9.12E-05
CED-nr	MJ	7.93E+00	1.42E-01	7.78E+00	6.16E-06	5.78E-03	1.44E-03
CED-r	MJ	2.31E+00	9.84E-01	1.32E+00	7.24E-07	9.35E-05	3.38E-04

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The analysis highlights those inputs related to the compressor's operation, namely the electricity consumption required from the grid, emerge as the main contributors to the environmental degradation.

In the case of the compressor, it has been estimated that its operation is 23,2 hours a day. It has been estimated that only two and a half hours of operation is required to remove 1 kg of ML, which underlines the efficiency of this equipment in waste management. However, this efficiency has the disadvantage that approximately 1.1 kWh of electricity is consumed for each kg of ML processed. Unless renewable energy sources are used, this consumption depletes fossil fuel resources and contributes to high emissions during the electricity generation process. The compressor produces virtually no emissions on-site, while other installations of the Bubble Barrier use 100% renewable energy, making sure that this impact is minimised.

On the other hand, Figure 17 and Table 16 provide a comprehensive overview of the environmental ramifications of the manufacturing processes employed in constructing the Bubble Barrier & solar panels. The analysis sheds light on the main contributors to environmental impact, highlighting the critical role played by various equipment components. The findings have highlighted the importance of one main component in driving environmental impacts.

Figure 17 Environmental impacts of the Bubble Barrier manufacturing stage: input/output analysis

Table 16 Environmental impacts of the Bubble Barrier manufacturing stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Bubble Barrier Main	Bubble Hose Assembly	Catchment System	Compressor Housing
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	1.56E-03	3.46E-05	1.50E-03	2.27E-05	1.39E-09
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	4.27E-01	5.29E-03	4.18E-01	4.01E-03	3.43E-07
ETX	CTUe	5.89E+00	4.56E-01	5.30E+00	1.35E-01	4.30E-06
PM	disease inc.	1.71E-08	3.22E-10	1.63E-08	4.87E-10	6.69E-15
EM	kg N eq	4.75E-04	7.19E-06	4.63E-04	4.29E-06	2.30E-10
EF	kg P eq	6.24E-05	6.20E-06	5.46E-05	1.65E-06	6.46E-11
ET	mol N eq	5.28E-03	7.77E-05	5.16E-03	4.33E-05	2.48E-09
HTc	CTUh	2.15E-10	3.04E-11	1.77E-10	7.09E-12	1.41E-16
HTnc	CTUh	3.92E-09	1.64E-10	3.67E-09	7.95E-11	2.41E-15
LU	Pt	3.67E+00	3.16E-02	3.62E+00	1.26E-02	8.42E-07
ADff	MJ	3.05E+00	6.46E-02	2.94E+00	4.47E-02	5.00E-06
ADe	kg Sb eq	3.73E-06	1.44E-06	2.20E-06	8.32E-08	2.13E-12
WU	m ³ depriv.	1.17E-01	1.33E-03	1.15E-01	8.15E-04	1.46E-07
CED-nr	MJ	3.24E+00	6.88E-02	3.12E+00	4.75E-02	5.29E-06
CED-r	MJ	1.59E-01	1.03E-02	1.44E-01	4.94E-03	3.63E-07

Firstly, the Bubble Barrier hose assembly has emerged as a significant contributor, accounting for 94.6% of the total environmental impact. Delving deeper into the composition of the bubble hose assembly, it has been seen that the predominant factor influencing its environmental impact is the use of concrete during its manufacturing (Babor et al., 2009). Since this structure is predominantly based on this material, the manufacturing process significantly increases environmental damage, mainly associated with the use of sand, limestone, hard coal, and gravel, required for its production (Nature, 2021).

Secondly, the compressor and housing emerge as the second key contributor, constituting 3.9% of the total environmental impact. This component is essential for the operation of the cleaning system. Upon closer examination, it has been found that the manufacturing of the compressor and the air cool dryer are the two components that cause the highest environmental impact during the manufacturing of the main Bubble Barrier system.

By identifying the main factors that affect the environment during the manufacturing of the Bubble Barrier, specific measures can be taken to reduce their impact and make the process more sustainable throughout the entire useful life of the system. These measures are researched for future installation.

A measure The Great Bubble Barrier is considering for future installations is to re-use depreciated concrete tiles as ballast of the tubing on the riverbed, instead of newly produced concrete tiles.

8.1.2 Seabed cleaning platform

This section presents the environmental impacts arising from ML cleaning using the seabed cleaning platform, encompassing all stages within the system's boundaries: manufacturing, installation, utilization, and EoL management of the equipment (Figure 18 and

Table 17). Conducting this type of analysis enables the identification of the stage that predominantly contributes to environmental impact, directing efforts towards process optimization and enhancing overall environmental performance. In addition, Figure 19 shows the network diagram considering the single score method.

Figure 18 Impact analysis for the Seabed cleaning platform considering all the stages involved in the technology

Table 17 Impact analysis for different stages of the Seabed cleaning platform: characterization results for each impact category

Impact category	Unit	Total	Equip. Manufact.	Equip. transport	Equip. Instal.	Equip. use&maint.	Transport to EoL	Equip. disposal
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	3.87E-03	4.09E-04	2.38E-06	5.89E-06	3.45E-03	7.15E-06	3.97E-07
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	8.18E-01	6.71E-02	1.09E-03	1.04E-03	7.45E-01	3.27E-03	6.91E-05
ETX	CTUe	6.34E+00	7.59E-01	7.65E-03	6.45E-03	5.54E+00	2.30E-02	7.57E-04
PM	disease inc.	5.27E-08	4.94E-09	8.12E-11	1.14E-10	4.73E-08	2.44E-10	6.70E-12
EM	kg N eq	1.56E-03	7.61E-05	6.01E-07	2.66E-06	1.48E-03	1.80E-06	1.31E-07
EF	kg P eq	7.80E-05	4.86E-05	7.75E-08	3.16E-08	2.90E-05	2.32E-07	1.59E-08
ET	mol N eq	1.67E-02	8.08E-04	6.11E-06	2.88E-05	1.58E-02	1.83E-05	1.31E-06
HTc	CTUh	8.94E-10	2.93E-10	4.97E-13	1.40E-12	5.98E-10	1.49E-12	3.59E-14
HTnc	CTUh	5.41E-09	2.39E-09	1.10E-11	3.74E-12	2.96E-09	3.30E-11	1.18E-12
LU	Pt	1.32E+00	2.53E-01	9.36E-03	9.08E-04	1.03E+00	2.81E-02	1.65E-03
ADff	MJ	1.22E+01	7.64E-01	1.55E-02	1.35E-02	1.14E+01	4.64E-02	1.14E-03
ADe	kg Sb eq	7.52E-06	7.24E-06	3.56E-09	3.60E-10	2.70E-07	1.07E-08	2.95E-10
WU	m ³ depriv.	5.48E-02	1.62E-02	6.38E-05	2.91E-05	3.83E-02	1.91E-04	4.14E-05
CED-nr	MJ	1.30E+01	8.11E-01	1.65E-02	1.43E-02	1.21E+01	4.94E-02	1.22E-03
CED-r	MJ	1.30E-01	6.72E-02	2.43E-04	7.67E-05	6.14E-02	7.30E-04	5.41E-05

Figure 19 Impact analysis for the Seabed cleaning platform considering the network diagram (single score method)

The results have shown that the stage that causes the most harm to the environment is the use and maintenance of the equipment. The impact of this stage constitutes roughly 70.9% of the total impact of the system, followed by equipment manufacturing with 28.4%. The remaining stages exhibit significantly lower environmental impacts, ranging from 0.46% to 0.03% in comparison.

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category impact is generated the greatest environmental, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 20). Weighting ranks or quantifies the contribution of an impact category to the overall impact, determining how significant an impact category is compared to other impact categories.

Figure 20 Impact analysis for the Seabed cleaning platform considering all the stages involved in the technology: weighing

The results of Figure 20 have highlighted four main categories with highest values: GW, ADff, ADe and PM. The results indicated that the high value in GW is closely related to the generation of CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ emissions. These emissions are linked to the use of the generator and the production (background processes) and use (foreground processes) of diesel and steel during the use and maintenance stages of the equipment, as well as in the manufacturing of the equipment (Holoppa, 2020; IEEE Staff, 2012).

In the case of ADff, this category is affected using oil, gas and coal, which are raw materials used in producing oil and coal (background processes). These resources are essential for the generation of energy and operation of machinery, which causes the depletion of natural resources (Shafiee & Topal, 2009).

On the other hand, in ADe the impact is related to the use of metals such as gold, tellurium and silver, which are used to produce active electronic components. The extraction and processing of these metals entails an intense demand for energy and resources, contributing significantly to the depletion of these non-renewable resources (Richards, 2006; Takayoshi Ueno et al., 1999).

Regarding PM, it has been observed that the impact is associated with the generation of PM_{2.5}, NO_x and SO₂ during the use of the generator, as well as in the production (background processes) and use (foreground processes) of energy and diesel. These emissions come primarily from the combustion of fossil fuels and other industrial processes, contributing to the air pollution and its adverse effects on human health and the environment (Horgan et al., 2022).

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The impact in these categories is closely related to the use of natural resources, the generation of polluting emissions and the production of essential components in the manufacturing and operation of equipment. Identifying these connections is crucial to implement effective mitigation measures and promoting more sustainable practices in the operations.

Figure 21 and Table 18 offer a more detailed view of the environmental repercussions of using and maintaining the equipment. This way of representing the results offers the possibility to show all the inputs and outputs associated to this stage, providing a comprehensive view of its environmental footprint.

Figure 21 Environmental impacts of Seabed cleaning platform use and maintenance stage: input/output analysis

Table 18 Environmental impacts of Seabed cleaning platform use and maintenance stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Generator operation	Lubricating oil	Paint	Diesel	Waste-recyc.	Waste-inciner.	Waste-landfill
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	3.45E-03	3.06E-03	1.79E-07	9.73E-08	3.03E-04	0	4.47E-05	4.17E-05
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	7.45E-01	5.93E-01	3.85E-05	2.04E-05	6.85E-02	0	7.81E-02	5.88E-03
ETX	CTUe	5.54E+00	3.36E+00	5.75E-04	3.39E-04	1.81E+00	0	3.19E-01	5.56E-02
PM	disease inc.	4.73E-08	4.35E-08	1.61E-12	9.36E-13	2.52E-09	0	3.94E-10	8.98E-10
EM	kg N eq	1.48E-03	1.38E-03	3.37E-08	1.77E-08	6.11E-05	0	2.41E-05	1.56E-05
EF	kg P eq	2.90E-05	1.77E-05	8.66E-09	4.70E-09	4.04E-06	0	5.75E-06	1.54E-06
ET	mol N eq	1.58E-02	1.49E-02	3.23E-07	1.79E-07	5.34E-04	0	2.05E-04	1.67E-04
HTc	CTUh	5.98E-10	5.49E-10	1.90E-14	2.22E-14	2.47E-11	0	2.14E-11	3.27E-12
HTnc	CTUh	2.96E-09	1.70E-09	5.07E-13	2.36E-13	4.72E-10	0	7.53E-10	3.67E-11
LU	Pt	1.03E+00	4.79E-01	1.40E-04	5.86E-05	2.34E-01	0	2.74E-02	2.90E-01
ADff	MJ	1.14E+01	7.03E+00	1.58E-03	5.35E-04	4.17E+00	0	4.92E-02	1.27E-01
ADe	kg Sb eq	2.70E-07	1.99E-07	3.22E-10	1.94E-10	4.81E-08	0	9.65E-09	1.19E-08
WU	m ³ depriv.	3.83E-02	1.56E-02	1.02E-05	1.07E-05	5.23E-03	0	1.20E-02	5.37E-03
CED-nr	MJ	1.21E+01	7.48E+00	1.68E-03	5.73E-04	4.43E+00	0	5.31E-02	1.35E-01
CED-r	MJ	6.14E-02	4.25E-02	3.48E-05	1.55E-05	1.49E-02	0	1.69E-03	2.18E-03

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The analysis highlights that inputs related to the generator's operation and the diesel consumption by the ship that are responsible for transporting the platform, emerge as the main contributors to the environmental degradation.

In the case of the generator, it has been estimated that its operation is 8 hours a day. It has been estimated that only half a minute is required to remove 1 kg of ML (28.8 seconds), which underlines the efficiency of this equipment in waste management. However, this efficiency has the disadvantage that approximately 0.125 kg of diesel has been consumed for each unit of ML processed. This consumption depletes fossil fuel resources and contributes to high emissions during the refining process. Furthermore, the environmental impact associated with the generator extends beyond diesel consumption, encompassing the emissions generated during its operation. These emissions, including carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, particles, and others, further aggravate the environmental burden.

Likewise, the diesel used to move the boat has adversely affected the environment. The LCA has revealed that the environmental impact has arisen from both diesel production, which requires oil extraction and refining processes, and from the emissions released during these processes.

On the other hand, the waste incineration represents a complex process with multifaceted environmental implications. Decarbonized water, an essential resource used in waste incineration, can create several environmental problems. Additionally, wastewater discharge from incineration plants may contain contaminants and chemicals, further affecting water quality and aquatic ecosystems. On the other hand, constructing incinerator plants involves significant inputs of materials and energy, including cement, for structural purposes. Cement production consumes a lot of energy and emits substantial amounts of CO₂, contributing to GHGs emissions and climate change. However, perhaps the most critical aspect of waste incineration is the release of emissions during the incineration process. The incineration of waste materials generates various pollutants, including GHGs, as well as other hazardous substances, such as dioxins and heavy metals. These emissions pose significant risks to both, human health, and the environment (Rigamonti et al., 2014).

In the case of ML treatment through disposal in sanitary landfills, the environmental impact has been closely tied to diesel consumption for specific process burdens and the construction of landfill infrastructure. Landfills require machinery and vehicles powered by diesel fuel for waste transportation, compaction, and other operational activities. Furthermore, the construction of landfill facilities involves land excavation,

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site preparation, and infrastructure development, all contributing to the environmental degradation (Siddiqua et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2014).

On the other hand, Figure 22 and Table 19 provide a comprehensive overview of the environmental ramifications of the manufacturing processes employed in constructing the seabed cleaning platform. The analysis sheds light on the main contributors to environmental impact, highlighting the critical role played by various equipment components. The findings have highlighted the importance of two main components in driving environmental impacts.

Figure 22 Environmental impacts of Seabed cleaning platform manufacturing stage: input/output analysis

Table 19 Environmental impacts of Seabed cleaning platform manufacturing stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Mobile platform	Main capsule	Smart camera	Supporting structures	Sensors	Floating platform	Aspiration system	Power generat.	Control room	Auxiliary container	Cables
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	4.09E-04	8.71E-06	1.06E-06	7.04E-07	1.49E-05	2.13E-06	1.59E-04	1.65E-06	1.14E-08	7.89E-05	1.12E-04	3.00E-05
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	6.71E-02	1.28E-03	1.59E-04	1.06E-04	3.58E-03	3.19E-04	3.78E-02	5.57E-05	2.43E-06	2.12E-03	1.69E-02	4.75E-03
ETX	CTUe	7.59E-01	2.75E-02	4.18E-03	2.79E-03	1.97E-02	8.52E-03	1.65E-01	1.79E-03	1.25E-05	8.68E-02	4.25E-01	1.75E-02
PM	disease inc.	4.94E-09	9.76E-11	8.58E-12	5.72E-12	2.53E-10	1.73E-11	2.96E-09	6.20E-12	1.15E-13	2.81E-10	9.48E-10	3.64E-10
EM	kg N eq	7.61E-05	1.32E-06	2.17E-07	1.44E-07	3.40E-06	4.39E-07	3.78E-05	1.09E-07	2.23E-09	4.66E-06	2.29E-05	5.07E-06
EF	kg P eq	4.86E-05	5.85E-07	2.06E-07	1.37E-07	1.50E-06	4.19E-07	1.67E-05	1.26E-07	7.61E-10	6.08E-06	2.11E-05	1.66E-06
ET	mol N eq	8.08E-04	1.34E-05	2.30E-06	1.53E-06	3.40E-05	4.67E-06	3.93E-04	1.39E-06	2.29E-08	6.13E-05	2.44E-04	5.28E-05
HTc	CTUh	2.93E-10	6.09E-12	1.16E-13	7.72E-14	1.45E-11	2.52E-13	2.25E-10	4.34E-13	1.66E-15	1.86E-11	1.69E-11	1.04E-11
HTnc	CTUh	2.39E-09	1.36E-10	5.69E-12	3.79E-12	4.31E-11	1.16E-11	4.27E-10	1.99E-11	3.07E-14	1.06E-09	6.03E-10	8.77E-11
LU	Pt	2.53E-01	6.62E-03	7.11E-04	4.74E-04	1.39E-02	1.46E-03	1.12E-01	6.52E-04	1.02E-05	2.77E-02	7.63E-02	1.29E-02
ADff	MJ	7.64E-01	1.50E-02	2.03E-03	1.35E-03	4.00E-02	4.06E-03	4.13E-01	7.01E-04	4.92E-05	2.44E-02	2.13E-01	4.98E-02
ADe	kg Sb eq	7.24E-06	1.56E-07	5.50E-08	3.67E-08	1.95E-08	1.12E-07	1.10E-07	1.94E-08	2.18E-11	9.35E-07	5.58E-06	2.19E-07
WU	m ³ depriv.	1.62E-02	1.04E-04	2.66E-05	1.77E-05	1.58E-04	5.34E-05	1.10E-02	2.87E-05	-1.73E-07	1.13E-03	2.83E-03	8.81E-04
CED-nr	MJ	8.11E-01	1.60E-02	2.16E-03	1.44E-03	4.25E-02	4.33E-03	4.38E-01	7.48E-04	5.28E-05	2.61E-02	2.27E-01	5.29E-02
CED-r	MJ	6.72E-02	1.80E-03	2.26E-04	1.51E-04	2.96E-03	4.64E-04	2.50E-02	1.53E-04	3.06E-06	4.01E-03	2.52E-02	7.19E-03

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Firstly, the floating platform has emerged as a significant contributor, accounting for the 45% of the total environmental impact. Delving deeper into the composition of the floating platform, it has been seen that the predominant factor influencing its environmental impact is the utilization of reinforcing steel. Since this structure is predominantly based on this material, the manufacturing process significantly increases environmental damage, mainly associated with the use of allied and non-allied steel, processing and transportation (Fente & Tsegaw, 2024).

Secondly, the control room emerges as another key contributor, constituting the 31.5% of the total environmental impact. This component is essential for the operation of the cleaning system. Upon closer examination, it has been found that the electronic components integrated within the control room exert the most significant influence on the environmental footprint. Active electronic components account for over 75% of the total impact (Takayoshi Ueno et al., 1999).

By identifying the main factors that affect the environment during the manufacturing of the seabed cleaning platform, concrete measures can be taken to reduce their impact and make the process more sustainable throughout the entire useful life of the platform.

To lower the environmental footprint of the cleaning system using the seabed cleaning platform, it is crucial to identify and propose measures to reduce the environmental impact. Following the LCA analysis, some key areas have been identified to improve sustainability and minimize the system's environmental impact. First, an optimization of energy efficiency should be considered. In this sense, it would be recommended to implement technologies and practices that reduce energy consumption during the operation of the generator. This would include using a more energy-efficient equipment. Another solution would be to transitioning to renewable energy sources. In this sense, exploring the viability of using renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind energy, to power the generator and thus reduce dependence on fossil fuels would be recommended. This alternative would not only reduce carbon emissions but also contribute to the energy resilience of the system. Using more sustainable alternative fuels for the generator and the boat, such as biofuels or green hydrogen, could also be considered. This measure could significantly reduce GHG emissions and improve air quality.

Regarding the impacts related to the manufacturing of the equipment, it is recommended to optimize the use of materials, exploring more sustainable material alternatives for the construction of the platform, thus reducing dependence on reinforcing steel, which is a large contributor to the environmental impact. This

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solution could include research and adoption of composite materials, recycled plastics, or materials from renewable sources.

Implementing these measures will not only contribute to reducing the environmental impact of the cleaning system and thus promote it as a sustainable solution to clean aquatic ecosystems.

8.2 Segregation and recycling technologies

8.2.1 AI-driven Robotic system

This section outlines the environmental impacts associated with the ML segregation process using an AI-driven robotic system. Similar to the cleaning technologies discussed previously, the segregation technology encompasses all stages within the system's boundaries: from manufacturing and installation to utilization and EoL management of the equipment (Figure 23 and Table 20). Additionally, Figure 24 presents a network diagram utilizing the single score method, providing an overarching visual representation of the system's environmental impact.

Figure 23 Impact analysis for the AI-driven robotic system considering all the equipments

Table 20 LCA for different stages of the AI-driven robotic system: characterization results

Impact category	Unit	Total	Equip. Manufact	Equip. transport	Equip. installation	Equip. use&maint.	Transport to EoL	Equip. disposal
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	4.63E-05	1.95E-05	2.47E-08	0.00E+00	2.67E-05	7.39E-08	9.24E-09
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	2.94E-02	3.84E-03	1.13E-05	0.00E+00	2.55E-02	3.38E-05	1.84E-06
ETX	CTUe	1.49E-01	3.85E-02	7.92E-05	0.00E+00	1.10E-01	2.37E-04	2.79E-05
PM	disease inc.	5.93E-10	2.66E-10	8.41E-13	0.00E+00	3.24E-10	2.52E-12	1.92E-13
EM	kg N eq	1.54E-05	4.14E-06	6.22E-09	0.00E+00	1.12E-05	1.86E-08	4.27E-09
EF	kg P eq	5.11E-06	2.31E-06	8.02E-10	0.00E+00	2.80E-06	2.40E-09	1.51E-10
ET	mol N eq	1.45E-04	4.17E-05	6.32E-08	0.00E+00	1.03E-04	1.89E-07	3.66E-08
HTc	CTUh	2.29E-11	1.54E-11	5.14E-15	0.00E+00	7.47E-12	1.54E-14	7.09E-16
HTnc	CTUh	3.37E-10	8.77E-11	1.14E-13	0.00E+00	2.48E-10	3.41E-13	1.14E-14
LU	Pt	9.00E-02	1.70E-02	9.69E-05	0.00E+00	7.26E-02	2.90E-04	5.57E-05
ADff	MJ	1.05E-01	4.48E-02	1.60E-04	0.00E+00	5.95E-02	4.80E-04	2.95E-05
ADe	kg Sb eq	3.35E-07	3.20E-07	3.69E-11	0.00E+00	1.49E-08	1.11E-10	2.30E-12
WU	m ³ depriv.	5.08E-03	1.38E-04	6.60E-07	0.00E+00	4.94E-03	1.98E-06	1.43E-06
CED-nr	MJ	1.12E-01	4.77E-02	1.70E-04	0.00E+00	6.32E-02	5.10E-04	3.13E-05
CED-r	MJ	1.05E-02	5.60E-03	2.52E-06	0.00E+00	4.91E-03	7.55E-06	4.46E-07

Figure 24 Impact analysis for the AI-driven robotic system considering the network diagram (single score method)

The findings underscore that the stage most significantly impacting the environment is the use and maintenance of the equipment. This phase alone accounts for approximately the 60.5% of the system's total environmental impact, as revealed by the analysis. The equipment manufacturing stage is closely behind, contributing the 39.28% to the overall environmental footprint. Notably, the remaining stages, including transportation stages and equipment disposal, exhibit markedly lower environmental impacts, with values ranging from 0.17% to 0.02% in comparison.

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category the most significant environmental impact is generated, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 25).

Figure 25 Impact analysis for the AI-driven robotic system considering all the stages involved in the technology: weighing

The findings depicted in Figure 25 shed light on two main categories with notably high values: GW and ADe. Specifically, the substantial value observed in the GW category is intricately linked to the generation of emissions such as CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄. These emissions are directly associated with treating ML deemed unrecyclable, specifically referring to treating municipal solid waste through incineration (Harris et al., 2015). Moreover, the emissions are closely tied to the production (background processes) and use (foreground processes) of electricity required during the equipment's use and maintenance stages and during its manufacturing process (Redko et al., 2024; Rigamonti et al., 2014; Siddiqua et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the ADe category primarily encompasses the environmental impact arising from the utilization of metals such as gold, silver, and tellurium. These metals play an essential role in the production of active electronic components and copper extraction processes. Gold and silver, renowned for their excellent electrical conductivity, are extensively utilized in manufacturing electronic components like connectors, cables, and electrical contacts. Similarly, tellurium finds application in semiconductor device production and is also involved in copper mining operations, among other uses (Richards, 2006; Takayoshi Ueno et al., 1999).

To gain a deeper understanding of the origins of impacts associated with the use and maintenance of the equipment, a comprehensive analysis has been conducted, delineating all inputs and outputs of this crucial stage. These findings are illustrated in Figure 26 and detailed in

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Table 21. By thoroughly examining these results, the specific factors contributing to the environmental impacts during the equipment's use and maintenance phase can be identified.

Figure 26 Environmental impacts of AI-driven robotic system use and maintenance stage: input/output analysis

Table 21 Environmental impacts of AI-driven robotic system use and maintenance stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Electricity	Waste- recycle	Waste - incineration	Waste - landfill
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	2.67E-05	4.57E-06	0.00E+00	1.34E-05	8.75E-06
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	2.55E-02	8.04E-04	0.00E+00	2.34E-02	1.23E-03
ETX	CTUe	1.10E-01	3.03E-03	0.00E+00	9.57E-02	1.17E-02
PM	disease inc.	3.24E-10	1.67E-11	0.00E+00	1.18E-10	1.89E-10
EM	kg N eq	1.12E-05	7.39E-07	0.00E+00	7.22E-06	3.27E-06
EF	kg P eq	2.80E-06	7.56E-07	0.00E+00	1.72E-06	3.22E-07
ET	mol N eq	1.03E-04	6.69E-06	0.00E+00	6.15E-05	3.50E-05
HTc	CTUh	7.47E-12	3.73E-13	0.00E+00	6.41E-12	6.87E-13
HTnc	CTUh	2.48E-10	1.48E-11	0.00E+00	2.26E-10	7.70E-12
LU	Pt	7.26E-02	3.53E-03	0.00E+00	8.22E-03	6.09E-02
ADff	MJ	5.95E-02	1.81E-02	0.00E+00	1.47E-02	2.66E-02
ADe	kg Sb eq	1.49E-08	9.53E-09	0.00E+00	2.90E-09	2.50E-09
WU	m ³ depriv.	4.94E-03	2.04E-04	0.00E+00	3.61E-03	1.13E-03
CED-nr	MJ	6.32E-02	1.89E-02	0.00E+00	1.59E-02	2.83E-02
CED-r	MJ	4.91E-03	3.95E-03	0.00E+00	5.08E-04	4.58E-04

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Based on the results obtained from this analysis, it has been evident that the primary factor contributing to environmental impact has been the incineration of waste that cannot be recovered through other means, accounting for the 50.5% of the total impact. This has been followed by the waste treatment through landfills (28.8%) and electricity consumption (20.7%). It is important to note that the assumption has been made that not all MLs can undergo recycling processes, hence a portion of this waste (4.5% of the total) has been estimated to be treated as municipal waste through incineration, while another portion (10.5%) has been directed to waste landfills.

These estimations have been made in collaboration with TEC partners; however, they are subject to change upon conducting a thorough study of all waste types and exploring alternative treatment methods for waste deemed unsuitable due to composition or degradation. Additionally, percentage variations could occur as waste volume estimates may fluctuate. Furthermore, the composition of segregated MLs may vary considerably.

Waste incineration is a complex process with diverse environmental implications. The use of decarbonized water in incineration can lead to environmental issues, while wastewater discharge from incineration plants may contain contaminants, affecting water quality. Constructing incinerator plants requires substantial energy and materials like cement, contributing to CO₂ emissions and climate change. However, the most critical aspect is the release of emissions during incineration, including GHG and hazardous substances like dioxins and heavy metals, posing risks to human health and the environment.

When treating ML through disposal in landfills, environmental impact is closely linked to diesel consumption for operational processes and construction of landfill infrastructure. Landfills rely on diesel-powered machinery and vehicles for waste transportation and compaction, while the construction process involves land excavation and infrastructure development, contributing to environmental degradation.

In the case of electricity consumption, the impact has been linked to emissions released during the generation and distribution processes. In addition, various sources are used for the electricity generation, including fossil fuels such as coal, oil, natural gas, and nuclear energy, as well as renewable sources such as wind, solar, hydro and biomass. Burning fossil fuels releases many atmospheric pollutants, including CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, and PM. These emissions contribute to air pollution and global warming, thereby increasing environmental degradation. Additionally, electricity distribution involves a vast infrastructure network, including power lines,

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substations, and transformers. The construction, maintenance, and operation of this infrastructure can have negative environmental consequences.

Although the segregation process proposed by the project has an environmental impact, there is room to improve waste management through increased segregation, thereby allowing for more efficient recycling processes. To illustrate this possibility, a comparison has been made between the proposed waste segregation process and the scenario of treating ML described earlier (Figure 27).

Figure 27 Comparison of ML management in an LCA context: Segregation process (MAELSTROM) and ML treatment (general context)

In the case of the segregation process, the treatment of ML has been divided as follows: 50% for recycling through processes defined within the project framework, 35% for recycling through other recycling methods, 10.5% for landfill management, and 4.5% for incineration. On the other hand, the comparison scenario suggests that 35% of ML could be managed through recycling, 50% through landfill disposal, and 15% through incineration.

This comparison reveals that through better waste segregation, the proportion of materials destined for recycling could be significantly increased, thereby reducing the amount of waste sent to landfills or incinerators. This would not only contribute to reducing the environmental impact associated with waste management but also promote a more circular and sustainable economy by encouraging resource reuse. Therefore, the importance of implementing effective waste segregation strategies to improve waste management and advance towards a more sustainable future is evident.

On the other hand, Figure 28 and Table 22 provide a comprehensive overview of the environmental ramifications of the manufacturing processes employed in

constructing the seabed cleaning platform. The analysis sheds light on the main contributors to environmental impact, highlighting the critical role played by various equipment components. The findings have highlighted the importance of two main components in driving environmental impacts.

Figure 28 Environmental impacts of AI-driven robotic system manufacturing stage: input/output analysis

Table 22 Environmental impacts of AI-driven robotic system manufacturing stage: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Perception and AI classification unit	Robot unit	Conveyor belts
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	1.94E-05	1.79E-07	3.64E-06	1.56E-05
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	3.84E-03	3.20E-05	5.98E-04	3.21E-03
ETX	CTUe	3.85E-02	2.05E-04	1.18E-02	2.65E-02
PM	disease inc.	2.66E-10	2.42E-12	3.21E-11	2.31E-10
EM	kg N eq	4.14E-06	3.41E-08	7.68E-07	3.34E-06
EF	kg P eq	2.30E-06	1.51E-08	5.99E-07	1.69E-06
ET	mol N eq	4.16E-05	3.45E-07	7.66E-06	3.36E-05
HTc	CTUh	1.54E-11	1.32E-13	6.83E-13	1.46E-11
HTnc	CTUh	8.76E-11	8.55E-13	1.82E-11	6.85E-11
LU	Pt	1.70E-02	1.28E-04	2.38E-03	1.45E-02
ADff	MJ	4.48E-02	3.64E-04	7.60E-03	3.68E-02
ADe	kg Sb eq	3.20E-07	1.37E-09	1.38E-07	1.80E-07
WU	m ³ depriv.	1.38E-04	1.09E-06	7.46E-05	6.25E-05
CED-nr	MJ	4.77E-02	3.87E-04	8.10E-03	3.92E-02
CED-r	MJ	5.59E-03	4.71E-05	8.31E-04	4.72E-03

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The environmental impacts associated with the three components of the equipment involved in this system have provided valuable insights into their respective contributions. The analysis has revealed that the conveyor belts exhibit the highest environmental impact, accounting for a substantial 77.8% of the total impact. The robot unit has been the following, contributing 21.5% to the overall environmental impact. In contrast, the perception and AI classification unit exhibit a comparatively lower environmental impact, representing only the 0.8% of the total impact. Although this unit plays a crucial role in the system by providing perception capabilities and AI-driven decision-making, its environmental footprint is relatively minor compared to the other components.

The substantial environmental impact attributed to conveyor belts has underscored their pivotal role within the system and emphasizes the significant environmental consequences associated with their operation. The impact of this equipment has been significantly influenced by the presence of active electronic components utilized within the conveyor belts (Richards, 2006; Takayoshi Ueno et al., 1999). As mentioned above, these components, which often contain precious metals such as gold, contribute to the environmental degradation due to the extraction and utilization processes involved in their production. Additionally, the use of alloyed steels in their construction has affected the environmental impact of the conveyor belts. The production of alloyed steels requires the extraction of raw materials, such as iron ore and other metallic elements, as well as energy-intensive processes for alloying and shaping. Moreover, transforming these alloyed steels into conveyor belt components further adds to their environmental footprint (Holappa, 2020).

Although the impact of the robot unit is less than that of conveyor belts, it represents a considerable part of the total impact. The impact of this equipment is related to the production of active electrical components and, to a lesser extent, to passive electronic components. As previously explained, the impact of the use of electrical components is related to the use of gold in their manufacture.

Consequently, the influence observed within these categories is deeply intertwined with the utilization of natural resources, the emission of pollutants, and the manufacturing of vital components necessary for the production and operation of equipment. Understanding these correlations is imperative to implementing effective mitigation strategies and promoting sustainable methodologies throughout our operations.

To lower the environmental footprint of the cleaning system using the AI-driven robotic system, it is crucial to identify and propose measures to reduce the

environmental impact. Following the LCA analysis, some key areas have been identified to improve the sustainability and minimize the system's environmental impact. First, an optimization of energy efficiency should be considered. In this sense, it would be recommended to implement technologies and practices that reduce energy consumption during the system's operation. This would include using more energy-efficient equipment or renewable energy sources (solar or wind energy).

On the other hand, to reduce the impact associated with the treatment of ML through incineration, seeking and using alternative waste-to-energy technologies can help reduce the environmental impact. The most effective way to reduce the environmental impact of waste incineration could be to minimize the amount of waste generated.

Regarding the impacts related to the manufacturing of the equipment, it is recommended to optimize the use of materials, exploring more sustainable material alternatives for the construction of the conveyor belts, thus reducing dependence on alloyed steel, which is a large contributor to the environmental impact. This solution could include research and adoption of composite materials, recycled plastics, or materials from renewable sources.

Implementing these measures will not only contribute to reducing the environmental impact of the cleaning system and thus, promoting it as a sustainable solution to clean aquatic ecosystems.

8.2.2 Thermoplastic recycling (additivation and shredding)

This section examines the environmental impacts associated with the thermoplastic recycling process of ML. Unlike cleaning and segregation technologies, which cover the full system boundaries, the recycling processes consider only the inputs and outputs specific to the process itself, excluding the manufacturing of equipment. As previously noted, the equipment has been omitted from the analysis due to its use at a laboratory scale and reliance on pre-existing commercial equipment.

The environmental results, capturing all inputs and outputs of the thermoplastic process, are presented in Figure 29 and Table 23. Additionally, Figure 30 provides a network diagram using the single score method, offering a comprehensive visual representation of the overall environmental impact of the system.

Figure 29 Environmental impacts of thermoplastic recycling: input/output analysis

Table 23 Environmental impacts of thermoplastic recycling: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Glass fibre	Tap water	Electricity	Transportation	Wastewater
AC	mol H+ eq	0,0065	0,0047	1,34E-05	0,0017	4,66E-07	1,45E-05
GW	kg CO2 eq	0,987	0,634	0,002	0,347	0,0002	0,0029
ETX	CTUe	2,275	1,468	0,00669	0,363	0,001	0,435
PM	disease inc.	4,21E-08	3,59E-08	1,39E-10	5,86E-09	1,65E-11	1,74E-10
EM	kg N eq	0,0014	0,0009	2,62E-06	0,0003	1,21E-07	0,0001
EF	kg P eq	0,0005	0,0002	1,63E-06	0,0003	1,50E-08	1,37E-05
ET	mol N eq	0,0132	0,0104	2,52E-05	0,0027	1,23E-06	4,56E-05
HTc	CTUh	7,05E-10	5,82E-10	1,09E-11	1,08E-10	9,24E-14	5,26E-12
HTnc	CTUh	3,85E-08	3,49E-08	1,42E-10	3,00E-09	2,10E-12	4,81E-10
LU	Pt	2,88	1,66	0,0096	1,19	0,0022	0,0143
ADff	MJ	16,28	8,27	0,044	7,93	0,0029	0,032
ADe	kg Sb eq	7,40E-05	7,33E-05	1,29E-08	6,85E-07	6,51E-10	1,43E-08
WU	m3 depriv.	0,138	0,123	0,337	0,081	1,30E-05	-0,404
CED-nr	MJ	17,31	8,92	0,05	8,31	3,15E-03	0,034
CED-r	MJ	2,15	0,62	0,0065	1,52	4,78E-05	0,0036

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Based on the results obtained, it appears that the main factor that has contributed to the environmental impact has been the glass fibre utilization in the final product assuming 76% of the total impact, and this is determined by its production. The second most significant factor has been the consumption of electricity for the equipment, representing 30,3%.

Figure 30 Impact analysis for the thermoplastic recycling considering the network diagram (single score method)

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category is generated the most significant environmental impact, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 31).

Figure 31 Impact analysis for the thermoplastics recycling considering all the inputs and outputs involved in the technology: weighting

The results of Figure 31 have highlighted three main categories with highest values: ADe, GW and ADff. On the one hand, in ADe the impact is related to the use of glass fibres. The glass fibres are typically available commercially in various chemical compositions, but most glass fibres are silica-based (approximately 50–60% SiO₂) and contain calcium borate and cooper concentrate used in glass fibres manufacturing. The extraction and processing of these metals entails an intense demand for energy and resources, contributing significantly to the depletion of these non-renewable resources.

The value in GW is closely related to the generation of CO₂, emissions mainly, followed by methane emissions. These emissions are linked to the manufacturing of the fibreglass, but also to the compounding of plastic where it is mixed with the added fibreglass, as well as the injection, where the reformulated pellet is introduced into the hopper of the injection machine to manufacture an injected part.

In the case of ADff, this category is affected by the use of uranium, coal, crude oil, and natural gas which are raw materials used for electricity generation (background processes) (Shafiee & Topal, 2009). These resources are essential for the generation of energy and operation of machinery, which causes their depletion.

As previously mentioned, the inventory data were derived from experiments conducted at a laboratory scale. In this context, the environmental impacts are directly tied to the scale of operations. As the scale increases, these impacts could be mitigated by employing more energy-efficient equipment, leading to reduced natural resource consumption and lower pollutant emissions. In addition, integrating

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renewable energy sources can play a crucial role in minimizing environmental impact. Utilizing solar, wind, or other renewable energies to operate equipment can decrease reliance on fossil fuels, thereby reducing emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs) and other air pollutants.

On the other hand, to reduce the environmental impact, it is crucial to explore alternatives to glass fibre by incorporating more sustainable materials or eco-friendly additives. This could involve the use of natural fibres such as flax, hemp, or bamboo, which not only have a lower carbon footprint but are also biodegradable. Additionally, developing bio-based resins or incorporating recycled materials into the manufacturing process can significantly reduce waste and energy consumption. However, it is important to assess whether the use of these materials is feasible without altering the structure or key characteristics of the final products.

In conclusion, reducing the environmental impact of recycling thermoplastics from marine waste requires a dual focus on energy efficiency and sustainable use of materials. In addition, scaling up these processes can improve energy efficiency and incorporate renewable sources, while exploring alternatives such as natural fibres can further reduce impacts. It is critical to ensure that these changes do not compromise the performance of the final products, thereby balancing sustainability with quality.

8.2.3 Hard-to-recycle plastics (thermal press molding)

The environmental outcomes, encompassing all inputs and outputs of this process, are depicted in Figure 32 and

Table 24. Furthermore, Figure 33 elucidates a network diagram utilizing the single score method, offering a complete visual representation of the system's overall environmental impact.

Figure 32 Environmental impacts of Hard-to-recycle plastics: input/output analysis

Table 24 Environmental impacts of Hard-to-recycle plastics: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Electricity	Water	Bonding agent	Colouring oxides
AC	mol H+ eq	4.16E-03	3.57E-03	1.32E-06	5.09E-04	8.24E-05
GW	kg CO2 eq	1.03E+00	9.05E-01	2.38E-04	1.16E-01	6.88E-03
ETX	CTUe	1.29E+01	7.57E+00	4.29E-03	5.31E+00	5.54E-02
PM	disease inc.	2.01E-08	1.38E-08	1.27E-11	4.65E-09	1.66E-09
EM	kg N eq	6.90E-04	5.74E-04	2.54E-07	9.18E-05	2.42E-05
EF	kg P eq	1.94E-04	1.63E-04	1.71E-07	3.09E-05	3.92E-07
ET	mol N eq	7.46E-03	6.16E-03	2.41E-06	9.61E-04	3.38E-04
HTc	CTUh	4.22E-10	2.01E-10	9.94E-13	2.14E-10	6.55E-12
HTnc	CTUh	7.23E-09	5.61E-09	1.40E-11	1.52E-09	8.95E-11
LU	Pt	2.53E+00	2.24E+00	9.63E-04	2.78E-01	1.38E-02
ADff	MJ	1.50E+01	1.27E+01	4.07E-03	2.22E+00	9.82E-02
ADe	kg Sb eq	6.40E-06	5.03E-06	1.17E-09	1.35E-06	2.17E-08
WU	m3 deprived	4.38E-01	1.88E-01	3.09E-02	5.55E-02	1.64E-01
CED-nr	MJ	1.59E+01	1.27E+01	4.07E-03	3.07E+00	9.82E-02
CED-r	MJ	1.09E+00	9.21E-01	1.53E-03	1.53E-01	9.53E-03

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Based on the results obtained, it appears that the main factor that has contributed to the environmental impact has been the consumption of electricity for the equipment, representing 76% of the average percentage impact compared to the total values. The second most significant factor has been the binding agent, with an overall average impact of 20%. Other inputs, such as colouring oxides and water, have exhibited significantly lower impacts, each contributing less than 4% to the total impact.

Figure 33 Impact analysis for the Hard-to-recycle plastics considering the network diagram (single score method)

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category is generated the most significant environmental impact, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 34).

Figure 34 Impact analysis for the Hard-to-recycle plastics considering all the inputs and outputs involved in the technology: weighting

The results reported above have shown that within the boundaries studied (gate-to-gate approach), the electricity supply has had the greatest environmental impact. In this context, energy itself has shown an overall average impact of around 76%. It is specified that the modelling has considered the national residual mix (AIB source). This impact could be due to the absence (for the process studied) of thermal consumption and the gate-to-gate boundaries, which do not include the impacts from the upstream phase (materials and transport). It is assumed that for electricity, the performance has been influenced by:

- Electricity injected, imported, and transformed.
- The transmission network and related losses.
- Direct emissions into the atmosphere (e.g., sulfur hexafluoride from the insulation of high voltage switchgear for medium voltage electricity demand).

These processes have influenced impact categories such as GW (with the release of quantities like CO₂, SO₂, NO_x), ADff, and ADe (with the use of abiotic resources for generating the electricity itself).

The second impact factor has been the binding agent. It is assumed that its performance has been influenced by the production of virgin raw materials, intermediate transport, and electricity for producing the material.

To conclude, the following sensitivity analysis has been developed (Table 25). This analysis is based on a scenario where energy consumption comprises 60% grid energy and 40% photovoltaic energy. The possibility of applying this scenario would lead to an overall average reduction of 13% across the investigated categories.

Table 25 Sensitivity analysis: energy variation

Impact category	Units	Total (Sensitivity analysis)*	Total (initial)	PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE
AC	μ Pt	3.08E-03	4,16E-03	-26%
GW	μ Pt	7.09E-01	1.03E+00	-31%
ETX	μ Pt	1.20E+01	1.29E+01	-7%
PM	μ Pt	1.76E-08	2.01E-08	-12%
EM	μ Pt	5,12E-04	6.90E-04	-26%
EF	μ Pt	1.56E-04	1.94E-04	-19%
ET	μ Pt	5,51E-03	7.46E-03	-26%
HTc	μ Pt	4.06E-10	4.22E-10	-4%
HTnc	μ Pt	7.80E-09	7,23E-09	8%
LU	μ Pt	1.84E+00	2.53E+00	-27%
ADff	μ Pt	1.05E+01	1.50E+01	-30%
ADe	μ Pt	8.85E-06	6.40E-06	38%
WU	μ Pt	4.05E-01	4.38E-01	-8%

*assumed 40% photovoltaic – 60% grid

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8.2.4 Temperature pyrolysis

This section delves into the environmental impacts linked with the recycling process of ML through the pyrolysis process.

The environmental outcomes, encompassing all inputs and outputs of the pyrolysis process, are depicted in Figure 35 and Table 26. Furthermore, Figure 36 elucidates a network diagram utilizing the single score method, offering a complete visual representation of the system's overall environmental impact.

Figure 35 Environmental impacts of pyrolysis: input/output analysis

Table 26 Environmental impacts of pyrolysis: characterization results for each input/output

Impact category	Unit	Total	Nitrogen	Compressed air	Electricity	Transport of degas	Degas - wastewater
AC	mol H ⁺ eq	3.04E-03	7.76E-08	5.70E-05	2.93E-03	4.66E-07	4.62E-05
GW	kg CO ₂ eq	6.08E-01	1.55E-05	9.70E-03	5.89E-01	2.04E-04	8.78E-03
ETX	CTUe	2.96E+00	4.57E-05	3.93E-02	1.67E+00	1.47E-03	1.25E+00
PM	disease inc.	1.06E-08	2.90E-13	2.19E-10	9.95E-09	1.65E-11	4.12E-10
EM	kg N eq	1.03E-03	1.42E-08	9.03E-06	5.22E-04	1.21E-07	4.99E-04
EF	kg P eq	5.78E-04	1.38E-08	9.16E-06	5.33E-04	1.50E-08	3.54E-05
ET	mol N eq	4.83E-03	1.27E-07	8.24E-05	4.60E-03	1.23E-06	1.51E-04
HTc	CTUh	2.02E-10	5.02E-15	6.09E-12	1.83E-10	9.24E-14	1.32E-11
HTnc	CTUh	7.15E-09	1.36E-13	2.13E-10	5.10E-09	2.10E-12	1.84E-09
LU	Pt	2.12E+00	5.60E-05	4.30E-02	2.03E+00	2.23E-03	4.47E-02
ADff	MJ	1.38E+01	3.52E-04	2.17E-01	1.35E+01	2.97E-03	9.57E-02
ADe	kg Sb eq	1.35E-06	3.33E-11	1.43E-07	1.16E-06	6.51E-10	4.15E-08
WU	m ³ depriv.	-1.28E+00	3.09E-05	2.48E-03	1.39E-01	1.30E-05	-1.42E+00
CED-nr	MJ	1.44E+01	3.69E-04	2.27E-01	1.41E+01	3.16E-03	1.01E-01
CED-r	MJ	2.64E+00	6.67E-05	4.83E-02	2.58E+00	4.78E-05	1.23E-02

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Based on the results obtained from this analysis, it has been evident that the primary factor contributing to environmental impact has been the electricity consumption for the equipment, accounting for the 82% of the total impact. This has been followed by the degas treatment (2.9%). Given that the treatment process has been assumed to be wastewater treatment, in the Ecoinvent process, this process includes water recovery, resulting in a positive impact on the WC category. If we exclude this positive impact, the environmental impact of degas treatment constitutes approximately the 10.2%. Other inputs exhibit significantly lower impacts, ranging from 2.3% to as low as 0.002%.

Figure 36 Impact analysis for the pyrolysis considering the network diagram (single score method)

Furthermore, to identify in which impact category is generated the most significant environmental impact, the results have been weighted for the impact categories of the PEF 3.1 methodology (Figure 37).

Figure 37 Impact analysis for the pyrolysis considering all the stages involved in the technology: weighing

Figure 37 shows that electricity exerts the most significant negative impact across all impact categories, especially in the GW, EF and ADff categories. This substantial impact arises primarily from the considerable energy requirements necessary to power the machinery involved in the pyrolysis process. The disproportionate impact of electricity can be attributed to the relatively limited input resources compared to the considerable energy demand of the machinery. This discrepancy is further accentuated by the gate-to-gate scope, which excludes impacts from machinery at MAKEEN and subsequent processing steps in the supply chain.

In addition, the impact of the electricity consumption in the GW and CED categories has been linked to the emissions released during the generation and distribution processes. In addition, various sources are used during electricity generation, including fossil fuels such as coal, oil, natural gas and nuclear, as well as renewable sources such as wind, solar, hydro and biomass. Burning fossil fuels releases many atmospheric pollutants, including CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, and PM. Additionally, electricity distribution involves a vast infrastructure network, including power lines, substations, and transformers. The construction, maintenance, and operation of this infrastructure can have negative environmental consequences. In addition to the aforementioned factors, the considerable impact of electricity also derives from activities related to the extraction of lignite and the treatment of waste from such mining operations.

Moreover, it is essential to note that ML, syngas, pyrolysis oil, and carbon black have not been included in the gate-to-gate scope. This exclusion could potentially affect

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the accuracy of the calculation and contribute to the disproportionate impact of electricity.

The specific Ecoinvent process utilized for electricity has been the "market group for electricity, medium voltage, RER". Consequently, the electricity mix is calculated based on the European average mix, and the results may not accurately represent the energy profile of a specific location or country. Therefore, it's conceivable that the impact from electricity could be lower if the energy mix at the treatment facilities of MAKEEN comprises a higher percentage of renewable energy sources specific to that location.

On the other hand, the process involving degas condensate has stood out among others due to its high level of uncertainties and assumptions. This watery solution typically contains organic material ranging from 1% to 5%. Within the impact assessment, several categories are significantly affected (ETX, EM and HTnc) by degas condensate. The impact of wastewater treatment is also closely linked to the generation of emissions that occur during the wastewater treatment process. During this stage, emissions of gases such as CO₂, CH₄ and volatile organic compounds may occur, as well as atmospheric pollutants such as suspended particles and organic compounds. These emissions can have significant consequences for air quality and the environment.

As mentioned above, Figure 37 illustrates that the impact of degas condensate on water consumption has been negative, indicating a positive contribution. This apparent contradiction arises because the degas condensate undergoes a waste treatment process, where the water is treated and returned to the environment. However, it's essential to note that the PEF3.1 methodology utilized in this assessment does not fully characterize the effects of Total Organic Carbon (TOC) on water quality, potentially introducing some limitations in the analysis.

Environmental impacts are closely related to the scale of operations. As the scale increases, the environmental impact could be reduced by using more energy-efficient equipment, resulting in a reduced consumption of natural resources, and decreased polluting emissions.

Furthermore, adopting renewable energy sources can significantly contribute to reducing environmental impact. By using solar, wind or other renewable sources to power equipment, dependence on fossil fuels can be reduced and, therefore, emissions of GHGs and other air pollutants can be reduced.

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Likewise, it is crucial to consider more sustainable alternatives to mitigate the impacts associated with degas treatment. This could involve the use of more advanced and efficient treatment technologies.

In summary, the scalability of operations offers opportunities to reduce the environmental impacts by implementing energy efficiency measures, using renewable energy sources, and adopting more sustainable alternatives for waste gas treatment. These actions can contribute to mitigate the climate change and preserve the environment, as well as to improve the efficiency and long-term profitability of industrial operations.

9 MAELSTROM Technologies development vs. Coastal Plastic Withdrawal: Environmental Impacts and Benefits

In this report, the LCA related to the whole life cycle of the technologies developed under the framework of the MAELSTROM project has been presented. This LCA has been conducted to identify hotspots where the environmental effects are most pronounced allowing for specific interventions to minimize the impact. Nonetheless, this analysis does not include the consequences of failing to collect plastic waste and the environmental impact on flora and fauna resulting from its presence in the aquatic ecosystems.

Commonly, LCA is the most used method for evaluating the potential environmental impacts. However, LCA is currently recognized as inadequate for effectively addressing the impacts resulting from marine plastic litter, a concern highlighted by international experts in the 2017 (Sonnemann & Valdivia, 2017). Among others, LCA datasets that specifically detail inventory flows related to product or process-specific plastic release into the environment have not been created yet. Furthermore, there is an absence of a well-defined and precise understanding of the relevant inventory flows (Loubet et al., 2022).

In relation to this, the marILCA project (MarILCA, 2019) funded by Plastics Europe (2019-2025), will allow for the integration of potential environmental impacts of plastic into LCA results. In the final phase of the project (2023-2025), a harmonized and consensus-based impact pathway framework and appropriate methods for addressing plastic litter impacts in LCA will be delivered. This will lead to a more comprehensive picture of potential environmental impacts, enabling the identification of trade-offs associated with the use of plastic and other materials in a product system.

In the absence of these final outcomes that will be obtained from the aforementioned project, this report does not provide a comparative analysis of the impacts associated with the development of the MAELSTROM technologies versus the potential effects on aquatic environments if the plastic were to remain in situ. However, these impacts do exist and can be highly detrimental, so they cannot be overlooked. In this sense, this section aims at conducting a thorough analysis of this issue, as despite the environmental impacts associated with the manufacturing of the MAELSTROM technologies the need to remove plastics from aquatic areas is undeniable.

9.1 The urgent need to remove plastics from the aquatic ecosystems

A substantial amount of plastic enters the ocean with estimates ranging from 6 to 12 million tons per year (Loubet et al., 2022). Plastic pollution in the environment is an increasing threat to ecosystems and human health since it not only contributes to plastic waste but is also at risk from plastic contamination due to plastic leakages (Loubet et al., 2022).

Plastic debris, once in the oceans, cause various harmful effects through different pathways. Entanglement and ingestion of large plastic particles have been documented in many regions worldwide. Additionally, larger plastic debris gradually breaks down over time turning into microplastics and nanoplastics. Due to their small size, it increases their bioavailability through ingestion, as they fall within the size range of prey for many marine organisms, and it is likely that these contaminants can be transferred through the consumption of other contaminated organisms (Lavoie et al., 2022). In fact, by means of fish and seafood consumption, humans ingest an estimated 39.000 to 52.000 plastic particles annually (Cox et al., 2019). Some studies even suggest that humans may also be exposed to microplastics and nanoplastics through inhalation (Wright & Kelly, 2017). Although knowledge of microplastic and nanoplastics toxicity remains limited, an even greater challenge lies in the fact that they may release their constituents, which can have their own toxic effects (Groh et al., 2019).

Furthermore, aging in plastics result in a higher degree of degradation, which can enhance their toxicity through the accumulation of degradation components within the particles. This aging process significantly changes the physicochemical properties of the plastics, thereby impacting their behaviour in the environment (Klasios et al., 2024). This is a problem when plastic remains in water over time, and unfortunately, it is hard to quantify. Furthermore, warmer temperatures and moisture levels alter even more the characteristics of plastics, thereby contributing to the release of hazardous substances (Wei et al., 2024). In addition to all this, accumulated plastics in beach sediments significantly affect thermal inputs and outputs, such as the absorption of infrared radiation, leading to temperature fluctuations that can profoundly impact terrestrial ectotherms (Jennifer L Lavers et al., 2021).

9.2 The significance of plastic recycling

In the context of the MAELSTROM project, various plastic recycling technologies have also been developed. Given that plastic is intrinsically linked to climate change

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throughout its entire lifecycle, including extraction and transportation of raw materials, manufacturing, waste treatment, their significance is noteworthy (Lavers et al., 2022).

In a conservative growth scenario, GHG emissions from primary plastic production are projected to exceed 4.75 gigatonnes of CO₂ equivalent by 2050, more than doubling current levels. These emissions would represent 21-26% of the remaining global carbon budget needed to limit average temperature rise to below 1.5°C (Karali et al., 2024). Furthermore, plastic production also adversely affects air and water pollution due to the involvement of various chemicals in the process. In addition, the reliance on non-renewable fossil fuels for plastic production leads to fossil fuel depletion, as well as the disposal of plastic waste, whether in landfills or through incineration, has detrimental effects on both wildlife and marine life (Saleem et al., 2023). Currently, fewer than 10% of plastics produced globally are estimated to be recycled, with the remainder being either disposed of in landfills or incinerated (UNEP, 2022). The recycling plastics could reduce GHG emissions by 77% compared to the production of virgin plastic, provided that 100% renewable energy is used throughout the entire process (Zheng & Suh, 2019).

In Figure 38 the estimated amounts of GHG released during the whole life cycle of plastic are presented (Zheng & Suh, 2019):

Figure 38 Estimated amounts of GHG released in CO₂ equivalent at each stage of the plastic life cycle (Zheng & Suh, 2019).

Figure 39 demonstrates how plastic impacts climate change by contributing to GHG emissions and interacting with climate change effects on the natural environment. The coloured shapes represent the connections between each component, plastic pollution, and climate change. Every stage of plastic production, from extraction to waste management, adds to GHG emissions, while climate change can intensify

extreme weather events and accelerate the dispersal of plastics into vulnerable and remote areas (Ford et al., 2022).

Figure 39. Interactions between plastic and climate (Ford et al., 2022)

Decreasing the demand for virgin plastics can lessen the sector's reliance on fossil fuels by emphasizing plastic recycling. To minimize the overall environmental impact of plastics, it is crucial to focus on the infrastructure related to extraction, production, and especially the end-of-life stages of plastic (Ford et al., 2022).

9.3 Project alignment with European environmental regulations

In alignment with the objectives of the European Green investments in R&D within the EU, every economic activity should be environmentally sustainable. For this reason, in June 2020, the Article 17 of the Regulation (EU) 2020/852 (Miralles et al., n.d.) on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment was settled, which is the basis for assessing whether an economic activity complies with the principle of not causing significant harm to the environment ("Do No Significant Harm").

An economic activity shall be considered to significantly harm when (Miralles et al., n.d.):

- it leads to significant GHG emissions;
- it leads to an increased adverse impact of the current climate and the expected future climate, on the activity itself or on people, nature or assets;
- it is detrimental to the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources;
- it leads to significant inefficiencies in the use of materials or use of natural resources such as non-renewable energy sources; and it leads to a significant

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increase in the generation, incineration, or disposal of waste; when it the long-term disposal of waste may cause significant harm to the environment.

- it leads to a significant increase in the emissions of pollutants into air, water or land, as compared with the situation before the activity started;
- it is significantly detrimental to the good condition and resilience of ecosystems; or detrimental to the conservation status of habitats and species, including those of Union interest.

According to the Article 9, every activity should meet most of the 6 environmental targets:

- ✓ Mitigation of climate change.
- ✓ Adaptation to climate change.
- ✓ Sustainable use and protection of water resources and marine resources.
- ✓ Transition to a circular economy.
- ✓ Pollution prevention and control.
- ✓ Protection and recovery of ecosystems and biodiversity.

9.4 Evidence of the critical importance of the MAELSTROM technologies development

It is evident that the MAELSTROM project remains fully compliant with the sustainability standards and contributes to advancing the overarching objectives of the European taxonomy - which sets rigorous criteria to ensure that projects contribute positively to environmental sustainability and are consistent with broader ecological goals - since the core objective of the project is to address the plastic pollution in marine environments which delivers substantial environmental benefits, advancing both environmental restoration and sustainability.

Notwithstanding that the development of the MAELSTROM technologies results in certain environmental impacts that cannot be entirely avoided - given that such impacts are inherent to the production of any technology - it is of paramount significance to emphasize its importance for addressing the critical issue of marine plastic pollution. On the one hand, implementing effective cleaning technologies is essential for mitigating the profound impacts plastic has on ecosystems and human health. On the other hand, recycling technologies play a pivotal role in combating climate change and reducing our reliance on virgin plastic production. Transitioning away from virgin plastic is crucial for achieving long-term environmental sustainability and ensuring the health of our planet for future generations.

10 Conclusions

In response to the adverse effects on marine biodiversity stemming from ML, the MAELSTROM project was launched. ML, has the potential to destroy aquatic habitats, harm marine life, and contaminate the food chain. Plastic pollution negatively impacts marine ecosystems, disrupting the balance of biodiversity within aquatic communities, and ultimately, entering the food chain, plastic also poses risks to humans through the consumption of contaminated fish.

Key objectives of the project include the assessment of the distribution and impact of ML on valuable ecosystems, the design of scalable and sustainable technologies to identify, remove, and classify ML, as well as raising public awareness and fostering collaboration with similar projects within and outside the European Union.

This deliverable has provided the findings of the thorough analysis of the environmental impacts of the technologies developed under the MAELSTROM project for the collection and recycling of ML applying a life cycle approach based on the ISO standards 14040:2006 and 14044:2006. The aim has been to identify the environmental impacts of each technology to pinpoint the most relevant areas for improvement, thereby enabling the reduction of the overall environmental footprint of the MAELSTROM project technologies.

The analysed technologies include, on the one hand, the following cleaning technologies: the Bubble Barrier, which addresses the issue of plastic waste floating on the surface and within the water column of rivers and canals; and the seabed cleaning platform, which represents an innovative approach to the removal of debris from the seabed and lower water columns using cable robotics. On the other hand, the following segregation and recycling technologies: the AI-driven robotic system, which addresses the urgent need for efficient and precise waste separation by employing advanced AI algorithms to enable the robot to recognize, identify, and separate various types of waste; thermoplastic recycling, aimed at processing diverse and heterogeneous marine plastic waste that has been collected and separated, and which is likely to be significantly degraded by saltwater and sunlight; hard-to-recycle plastics technology, an innovative approach for recycling fibre-reinforced composites and thermosetting matrix rigid foams that would otherwise be destined for landfills; and pyrolysis technology, which utilizes a temperature pyrolysis prototype to recycle ML.

The key findings of the environmental analyses of the various technologies are listed below:

- Regarding the Bubble Barrier, the findings indicate that the stage with the greatest environmental impact is the operation and maintenance of the equipment, followed by its manufacturing. The analysis underscores that the primary contributors to environmental degradation are associated with the compressor's operation, specifically the electricity consumption required from the grid. Concerning the environmental implications of the manufacturing processes for the Bubble Barrier and its associated solar panels, the hose assembly has been identified as a significant contributor. The predominant factor influencing its environmental impact is the use of concrete in its construction.
- Concerning the Seabed Cleaning Platform, the environmental impact is predominantly attributed to the use and maintenance of the equipment, followed by the manufacturing of the equipment. This impact is primarily associated with the operation of the generator and the production and use of diesel and steel during maintenance and manufacturing activities. The analysis reveals that the generator's operation and the diesel consumption required for the transportation of the platform are the principal factors contributing to environmental degradation.
- Regarding the AI-driven robotic system, the findings emphasize that the most significant environmental impact arises from the use and maintenance of the equipment and the equipment manufacturing stage is closely behind. These impacts are primarily linked to the processing of ML considered unrecyclable, particularly in the incineration of municipal solid waste. To address the environmental impact associated with the incineration of ML, it is advisable to seek and implement alternative waste-to-energy technologies. These measures can significantly contribute to reducing the overall environmental impact.
- Regarding the thermoplastic recycling, primary factor is the use of glass fibres, due to the extraction and processing of contained metals since it entails an intense demand for energy and resources, contributing significantly to the depletion of non-renewable resources. It is followed by the emissions related to the manufacturing of the fibreglass, as well as the compounding and injection processes.
- Regarding the hard-to-recycle plastics technology, the primary factor contributing to the environmental impact is the consumption of electricity for the equipment. An overall average reduction of 13% across the investigated impact categories could be achieved if energy consumption is allocated as 60% grid energy and 40% photovoltaic energy.

- Regarding the pyrolysis technology, the main contributor to environmental impact is the electricity required to operate the machinery used in the pyrolysis process. Utilizing renewable energy sources could significantly reduce this impact. By switching to solar, wind, or other renewable energies for powering the equipment, reliance on fossil fuels can be diminished, thereby decreasing emissions of greenhouse gases and other air pollutants.

As previously outlined in section 7, it is acknowledged that the environmental impacts associated with the development of any technology cannot be entirely eradicated, as some degree of impact will invariably arise at different stages of the life cycle. Nevertheless, these analyses have enabled the identification of the key areas that can be addressed through focused improvements thereby enabling a significant reduction in the associated environmental impacts.

In any event, the importance of removing plastic from coastal areas cannot be overstated, as it plays a crucial role in preventing ecosystem degradation and safeguarding human health. The accumulation of plastic waste in these environments can lead to severe ecological consequences, such as habitat destruction, entanglement of marine life, and ingestion of plastics by various species. This not only disrupts the balance of marine ecosystems but also poses a threat to biodiversity. Moreover, the presence of plastic in coastal regions can have direct implications for human health. As plastics degrade, they release harmful chemicals and microplastics into the environment, which can enter the food chain through contaminated seafood. This can result in health risks for humans, including exposure to toxic substances and potential long-term health effects.

Effective management and cleanup efforts are vital in mitigating the adverse impacts of plastic pollution and fostering healthier and more sustainable environments. For that, collaborative efforts from governments, businesses, and individuals are essential to address climate change, protecting marine ecosystems, and promoting a sustainable future. In this direction, it is imperative to support and invest in projects such as the MAESLTROM project dedicated to the collection and recycling of plastics from the aquatic ecosystems.

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